

Baseline Report

AETHERIA

Group 11: Hydrogen-based long-range eVTOL designed for crashworthiness

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Executive Overview

In recent years, the research and development for alternative means of travel have surged in search for faster, more efficient and more sustainable travel options. Moreover, increasing congestion and air pollution require ever more urgent solutions. Electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing (eVTOL) aircraft have the potential to be the solution to this problem. This new type of aircraft provides capabilities of flying over a congested city in a matter of minutes and providing point-to-point transport. An extension of the eVTOL design is the inclusion of hydrogen-based propulsion, which will yield a larger possible range for the aircraft. Therefore, this DSE project will focus on using hydrogen to increase the efficiency of long-range eVTOLs powered by batteries. The Mission Need Statement (MNS) of the project is as follows:

Design a sustainable long-range hydrogen eVTOL for crashworthiness that can transport four passengers

This report serves as the foundation based on which the final detailed design will be made. Literature studies on the current eVTOL market, as well as technical risks and requirements assessment and a sustainability analysis, are done. Finally, some preliminary designs are presented which will be further investigated in future reports.

Market Analysis

In order to gain an accurate understanding of the market size and potential, an in-depth market analysis was performed. The first step was to get an overview of the target demographic. This gave 6 main sectors (in order of most promising to least): Commercial travel, private usage/leisure, cargo transporting, structure inspection/maintenance, first responders and military applications. The ranking was based on mainly the user requirements, as well as the current amount of eVTOLs in the respective sector. It is therefore easier to enter the commercial travel market and the 4 passenger requirement also fits this. The existing designs can be categorized into 4 lift technology categories: Multirotor, lift + cruise, tilt wing, and tilt duct/rotor. These designs are used in the design options to come up with the first designs.

The range is an important factor of which requirements are made which alter design choices. The range of the design was calculated using a GDP range calculation. Two main regions were located as main markets: Western Europe and the USA. Then a program calculated which cities with a high GDP are within 300 km of each other. This was repeated for a range of 350 km and 400 km. Not enough cities were found to be connected when increasing the range to 400 km, although a large number of cities could be connected through a direct flight. This was seen as a large benefit, as several high-value connections, mainly with London, have become direct. The champion case is Amsterdam - London, as the range is just inside 400 km (359km) and the connection does not contain a quick rail connection (4h).

To perform an accurate cost estimation, a mission was set out. The mission consists of 3 flights per day of maximum range with a full payload, and 200 working days per year. Combining it with an operational lifetime of 15 years, the total capital expenditures (CAPEX) would be 2 million euros, and the operational expenditures (OPEX) would be 1.5 million euros per year. This gives a total cost of 24.5 million euros over its operational lifetime. The costs per passenger mile plays a vital role in determining the OPEX. It is assumed to be higher than that of a eVTOL fully on batteries, since hydrogen fuel costs are higher than that of electricity.

To compete with high-speed trains, the cruise speed requirement was found such that it matched or exceeded their speed. Existing eVTOLs having similar mission profiles have cruise speeds between 280 and 330 km/h, while high-speed rail has a speed of around 300 km/h (in Europe). The cruise speed has therefore been chosen at 300 km/h. With this speed, the block (door-door) time from the Canary Wharf, London to La Défence, Paris is 1 hour and 15 min, compared to the block time of 4 hours when taking the train (Eurostar). Although the price will be higher compared to high-speed rail, €480-€640 and €316 respectively, the saved time will make up for that.

In the next section the expected market share was calculated. This differs per region: The European obtainable market share of the team's eVTOL is the highest (8%) followed by the North American obtainable market share (5%). Furthermore, it is important to take into account to total market share the eVTOL branch could obtain. This is the highest for the North American market at 55%. Finally, the production size was calculated

at a total of 445 units. The first units will focus on the European market followed by the American market.

The preliminary mission profile is designed in 9 segments. The aircraft will first taxi to its take-off location. This takes negligible energy. The second segment is the hovering climb which takes approximately 10 seconds. This takes up a small but certainly not negligible amount of energy. The transition phase follows, where the aircraft switches from its vertical configuration to its horizontal configuration. This takes about 20 seconds. The cruise segment is the most energy-consuming since it requires a decent amount of power for a long time. Finally, loiter has also been taken into account to compute the total energy consumption over a 400 km flight, which is 534 kWh. Assuming a payload of 4 passengers this leads to 333 Wh/passenger km. This is competitive with other eVTOLs already designed.

Requirements

Subsequently, the requirement analysis led to interesting findings on how user requirements and regulations set by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) will impact the mission profile and design of the eVTOL. In total, three key user requirements were established which should be valued greatly. The first being that the aircraft shall have a range of 300 km. Next, hydrogen shall be used as a power source for the aircraft. Finally, the aircraft shall comply with EASA regulations regarding crashworthiness.

Critically reviewing these requirements yielded a discussion on which requirements should be altered to meet the intended purposes of the eVTOL to be designed. As mentioned in the market analysis, a 400 km range would substantially increase the potential market share in Europe. Hence, this user requirement was changed to fit this demand. Additionally, comparing the industry standards for passenger weight with the initial user requirement brought about an increase in maximum payload from the original 475 kg to 510 kg. The maximum payload then includes four passengers and one pilot including luggage.

Furthermore, besides the user requirements, other requirements which may influence the design are regulations set by EASA. The regulations the aircraft should adhere to impose a limit on the Maximum Take-Off Mass (MTOM) of 3175 kg [1]. This is not seen as a critical requirement as the estimated MTOM is well below this limit. Thereafter, regulations on safety, reliability and noise constraints do not inflict immediate significant limitations on the design but should be taken into account in later phases of the design.

To continue, stakeholder requirements contain some constraints on the aircraft dimensions, in-flight accelerations, financial yearly revenue, and overall costs. At first, it was not yet possible to set well-defined constraints for most of these requirements. This is due to fluctuations in the possible designs and a lack of knowledge of the financial aspect of eVTOLs. However, from the market analysis, a better understanding of the cost image of eVTOLs was acquired which yielded some rough first-order estimates for the unit production costs, generated yearly revenue, and total lifetime aircraft cost. Respectively, values of €3 million, €1.8 million, and €24.5 million were estimated.

Technical Risk Assessment and Management

A technical risk assessment has also been performed. First, various risks were identified which were then assessed on likelihood and consequence. The two most concerning risks were numerical/model errors and assumptions which might turn out to be inaccurate regarding the design. During Aetheria's operations, hydrogen safety and loss of power are an example of the risk. For each of the risks, a prevention and contingency plan has been set up, after which effect of these risks are much lower.

Sustainability Analysis

The sustainability analysis investigates multiple pillars. These pillars consist of environmental analysis, social analysis and economical analysis. The environmental analysis investigates four possible propulsion systems: Hydrogen combustion, hydrogen via a fuel cell, hybrid and battery-electric. The hydrogen combustion is not looked into as it emits NO_x gasses which are a big contributor to smog and acid rain. The analysis of the other three systems has been done by performing a life cycle analysis (LCA). This is split up into a cradle to gate (CTG) analysis, which assesses the production of the aircraft, and a well-to-shaft (WTS), which evaluates the operational emissions of the aircraft due to emissions in hydrogen and electricity production, battery or

fuel cell production and drive train losses. The analysis found that a lighter aircraft, even if it is made out of composites was beneficial to the environment. In addition, hydrogen fuel cells are more sustainable than batteries due to the harm done to the environment during mining.

From the social analysis two requirements have been found. One states the cabin noise shall be lower than 80 dB while the second one states the longitudinal acceleration during nominal flight shall not be higher than 0.6g. Thereafter, the economical analysis focuses on fuel costs, availability of the fuel and refuelling and storage. The fuel costs analysis found that the hydrogen production costs will halve in the future, but it is unsure how much the consumer price will drop, with opportunistic values ranging as low as 3\$/kg. The price drop depends on the price of electricity, since the green hydrogen is produced from electrical energy, improvements in the electrolysis efficiency and improvements in storage and transport. The availability is a positive aspect when considering hydrogen as a fuel. Grey hydrogen might not have a high availability sustainability as it is produced out of fossil fuels, but green hydrogen does as it is produced from electricity. Finally, the refuelling and storage of hydrogen is expected to innovate since the transport sector has been implementing hydrogen. Hydrogen gas stations already exist which might be usable for refuelling the VTOL, when placed near the vertiport.

Design Options

Following all the theoretical research done so far, some designs can now actually be considered or discarded based on the different analyses done. This process was done by first constructing a design option tree in which all possible configurations are examined. From all the categories that were considered (structure, aerodynamics, ground operations, crashworthiness, cabin configuration, power/energy and propulsion), different ideas were brought forward but were eliminated as an option if deemed unfeasible or undesirable.

Afterwards, some assumptions were made based on the engineering judgment of the project team to narrow down the scope of feasible designs. From this analysis, four ideas came forward as the most promising which can be divided into two categories: a tilt wing design and a tilt rotor (vectored thrust) design. Tilt wing eVTOLs have the capability to rotate the orientation of the entire wing depending on the flight phase (vertical or horizontal flight). The first proposed design was a conventional aircraft with tilting wings and two tilt rotors attached to the horizontal tail and/or canard. Secondly, a tilting tandem wing design is considered, similar to the Wigeon design of a DSE group from two years ago. The Wigeon design is illustrated in Figure 1a¹. For the second category, the first option is to design a conventional aircraft with a low number of tilt rotors. Then, the second option is to create a design with vectored thrust by rotating pods or distributed rotors, much like the Lilium Jet shown in Figure 1b².

(a) Tilting tandem wing, similar to Wigeon

(b) Lilium Jet

Figure 1: Two possible design configurations

Finally, four options were explored and analyzed as power options for the aircraft. Hydrogen as the only power source was deemed an unfeasible option as the current fuel cell technology will not be able to deliver the required power as such a powerful unit would require a tank size too substantial to be put in the fuselage of the aircraft. Therefore, batteries will most-likely be included in the design to provide the additional required power, although no final conclusions were drawn on this aspect yet.

¹Accessed May 3rd, <https://www.saullocaastro.nl/projects/wigeon>

²Accessed May 3rd, <https://lilium.com/jet>

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Symbols & Abbreviations

CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CFRP	Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics
CTG	Cradle-To-Gate Analysis
CtQs	Critical to Quality parameters
dB	Decibel
DOT	Design Option Tree
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EI	Emission Index
EOL	End-of-Life
eVTOL	electric Vertical Take-off and Landing
FCEV	Fuel cell electric vehicle
g	Earth's gravitational acceleration at sea-level
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GMP	Gross Metropolitan Product
GWP	Global Warming Potential
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
LHV	Lower Heating Value
MTOM	Maximum Take Off Mass
OEW	Operating Empty Weight
Pax	Passengers
RPM	revolutions per minute
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
SWOT	Strengths Weaknesses Opportunities Threats
TBD	To Be Determined
TLOF	Touch-down and lift off area
UAM	Urban Air Mobility
WTS	Well-to-Shaft Analysis

Market Analysis

A market analysis was performed in order to assess the market size and potential of the product. Establishing the competitive price and market size for the goods or services the product can offer is the main objective of the market analysis. This is based on the current market for comparable goods and services and an evaluation of the additional value of potential new technologies. It can also give an indication of how well the eVTOL would perform in both the current and the prospective market.

1.1. Target Sectors & Market Trends

To start designing the eVTOL, the target demographic must be known. A list was made of demographics ranked from most promising to least. This means the eVTOL would be tailored toward that sector. The team decided on the following:

1. Commercial Travel
2. Private Usage/Leisure
3. Cargo Transporting
4. Structure Inspection/Maintenance
5. First Responders (Police, Ambulance, Firefighters, Natural Disaster)
6. Military Applications

The ranking has been decided based on the user requirements, but also mainly the number of eVTOLs/helicopters currently in the respective sector. This makes it easier to enter the sector as a new eVTOL. Commercial travel has been ranked as the most important since the user requirements state that four passengers should fit. This makes the eVTOL more tailored toward commercial travel. The eVTOL can also be sold all together to a private company/person for leisure. Cargo transporting is also a possibility but it has been ranked slightly lower since only 500kg of payload can be carried, which, by cargo standards, is not very much. Structure inspection could be a possibility for highways or offshore wind farms, due to the distances that need to be covered. First responders generally do not need a lot of range and are therefore not a target sector. Military applications have been ranked last as this usually requires the easy assembly of specific instrumentation which is not something that is being designed for. It usually requires other accreditation as well ¹.

1.1.1. Market Trends

Markets and Markets has done an analysis into the eVTOL market and found these trends. Note that CAGR stands for compound annual growth rate, a measure of the projected growth. ²:

1. The hydrogen-electric hybrid eVTOLs are projected to see the highest CAGR
2. The piloted segment is projected to see the highest CAGR
3. The last mile delivery segment is projected to see the highest CAGR
4. The 100-1,000 kg segment is projected to see the highest CAGR
5. The segment with a range longer than 200km is projected to see the highest CAGR

¹ Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://english.defensie.nl/topics/military-aviation-authority/accredit>

² Accessed April 26th 2023, https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/evtol-aircraft-market-28054110.html?gclid=CjwKCAjw160iBhA2EiwAuUwWZSjathr3v3yT_OHA4NXnApe3kRqR-TDThvEFZ0wEi1tx00UzggDgshoC-twQAvD_BwE

When looking at the trends, it is clear that three of these trends comply with the user requirements, namely trends 1, 2, and 5. Trend 3 does not match the user requirements, as our goal is to satisfy passengers looking for a travel time of 1-3 hours, and a range up to 400 km while the last mile delivery focuses on short-range (0-30km). Our mass will also be a lot larger due to the long-range requirement meaning trend 4 also does not match. The user requirements matching most of the market trends indicate that the team's eVTOL can hold quite a substantial market share.

1.2. Range

Range has a significant impact on the total market share of the UAM industry [2], therefore finding a both suitable and feasible range is paramount. In order to do, the assumption was made that the amount of travel to and from a city is proportional to the Gross Metropolitan Product (GMP), the validity of this assumption is high as GMP is often used in computing passenger flow [3, 4]. Additionally, Brons et al. mentions that demand in air transport is largely determined by the spending capacity of the customer [5, pg. 1]. The analysis will mainly be limited to West Europe for reasons which will follow in this section. For this purpose, the cities in Table 1.1 were used, where all cities have a GMP higher than €159.2 billion. An evaluation of the North American market has also been performed together with a discussion on how compatible the markets are.

Table 1.1: List of cities with a GMP higher than €159.2 used in Figure 1.1³.

Major Cities in Europe					
Paris	Madrid	Milan	London	Dortmund	Rome
Munich	Berlin	Amsterdam	Barcelona	Hamburg	Dublin

Europe

Using the Python script, the accessibility of each major city in Europe was mapped. In Figure 1.1, radii are drawn around the cities listed in Table 1.1. All cities included in the map have a GDP higher than €159.2 billion. Color-coded radii indicate the cities that are within range of other cities, with a variety of colors for better distinction but no other intrinsic meaning. The black radii indicate that an isolated city and is not able to fly to another city in Table 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Visualization of cities listed in Table 1.1 with their corresponding radii. The radii are color-coded to represent the cities' ability to reach other cities within the specified range, with a variety of colors for better distinction but no other intrinsic meaning. The black radii indicate isolated cities that cannot fly to any other cities listed in Table 1.1.

From Figure 1.1a it can be seen that using a range of 300 [km] severely limits the amount of cities the VTOL would be able to fly to. Hence, the 300 [km] range requirement would severely limit the market for Aetheria. By increasing the range from 300km to 350km, it can be seen in Figure 1.1b that Central Europe opens up.

³Accessed May 4 2022, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/met_10r_3gdp/default/table?lang=en

Further increasing the range to 400 [km] has no effect on the isolated cities. Madrid, Barcelona and Rome are still isolated and hence the further increased range does not add to the usage of Aetheria.

However, from an accessibility point of view increasing the range to 400 [km] range allows for more high-value direct routes. Meaning, that instead of flying Amsterdam-London via Brussels one directly flies from Amsterdam to London. Direct flights are invaluable to the success of the project as direct flights significantly increase the block speed, also interchanges/transfers form a hard barrier for commuters and decrease rider-ship [6, 7]. Significant direct routes that would be achieved when increasing the range from 300 to 400 [km] are listed in Table 1.2. The combined GDPs of all trips are substantial and thus would be worth considering increasing the range to accommodate these flights. Additionally, considering the fact that Europe is relatively not a large market for eVTOLs, being able to establish oneself in these major cities as an eVTOL company early on would give the company an advantage.

Table 1.2: Direct flights with a combined GDP higher than €800 billion made possible by increasing the range from 300 [km] to 400 [km]

Trip	Range	Combined GDP [€ billions]
Paris - London	342	€ 1544
Amsterdam - London	359	€ 984
Brussels - London	320	€ 949
Paris - Lyon	393	€ 831

Figure 1.2: Visualization of relevant cities in America with their corresponding radii indicating their reachability within a 300km range (circles are at half scale for clarity reasons). The radii are color-coded for better distinction, but hold no other intrinsic meaning. The black radii indicate isolated cities that cannot fly to any other cities listed in Table 1.1. Only cities with a GDP per capita higher than 70,000 dollars are shown

North America

The same can be considered for North America. In Figure 1.2, the sizes of the circles have been made smaller for clarity reasons. In the 300km, 350km, and 400km range, there are 17,14,12 isolated cities respectively. The cities introduced are relatively small and would not significantly increase the market share of the eVTOL.

The East Coast of North America seems the most promising. Major cities like Boston, Washington, and New York lie in close vicinity to each other. The GDP of these cities is gigantic, e.g. New York has a GDP of €1.44 trillion. In contrast to Europe, increasing the range in North America is not as effective as for the European market due to the close vicinity and large market share of the major cities on the East Coast.

An exception on the general non-viable distances is the route between Los Angeles and Las Vegas, it is the busiest flight route in the US. The route has an average of 352 flights between them each week⁴. The travel distance of this route is 366 km, thus an eVTOL route between these cities could have a substantial influence on the size of the commercial market for Aetheria. This is another reason why increasing the range to 400km would be advantageous.

Conclusion on Range Estimation

The decision was made to size the aircraft based on the European market as this market is more suitable for long-range UAM. As was seen in Table 1.2 from the European market case, a large benefit was acquired in direct trips and decreasing the number of isolated cities when increasing the range. Building on this, the trip

⁴Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://simpleflying.com/what-are-the-usas-busiest-domestic-air-routes/>

Amsterdam - London was chosen as our limit/champion case. The reason is that the trip has the second largest combined GDP but also comes with a significant range penalty of 359 [km]. In contrast, increasing the range to 393 [km] in order to serve Paris-Lyon would not be worth it. This would mean the final design range should be 359 kilometers. However, the accuracy of this distance might not be exact due to the vertiport being at the outskirts of the city or any deviations from the optimal trajectory, meaning contingencies should be utilized. A contingency of 10% was chosen, arriving at 400 [km].

Table 1.3: Table containing the conclusions on the range analysis of the market

Parameters	Value
Preliminary Range	360 [km]
Contingency	10%
Final Range	400 [km] ⁵

1.3. Cruise Speed

Cruise speed is an important mission parameter as it is the main parameter with which the block speed can be controlled. The block speed is crucial to leverage the market as according to [Hae Choi and Park](#), larger fare prices can be charged for a larger reduction in travel time compared to normal public transport/taxi services [2, pg. 275].

Table 1.4 displays many eVTOLs and their respective cruise speeds. Based on a range of 400km, and a user requirement that the duration of the trip may take between 1 and 3 hours, this gives a range of cruise speeds of 133 km/h to 400 km/h. The eVTOLs with the largest market share are Lilium, Joby, Archer, and Vertical Aerospace, Aetheria's cruise speed should be competitive with these companies. These speeds are 280, 322, 241, and 322 kilometers per hour. Besides competition from the eVTOL market, the current best solution for sustainable travel, High-speed rail (HSR), will be our main competitor as they have a similar mission, high-capacity and are likely to be cheaper. Both the Eurostar and the Thalys reach speeds of 320⁶ and 300⁷ kilometers per hour respectively.

Thus, in order to stay competitive with HSR and existing VTOLs, a cruise speed of 300 km/h was decided upon. Reason being that Aetheria would be significantly faster than HSR due to the similar speed and our advantage in straight trajectory. Additionally, the Aetheria would fly at the same speeds as competing eVTOLs and finally, with current technology, a speed of approximately 300 kilometers per hour should be feasible.

1.4. Current eVTOL Market & Competition

From studying relevant literature, comparable products were found, based on which an estimate for the production costs as well as the cost per passenger mile could be made. Examples of products with similar user specifications are among others the Lilium Jet, Joby Aviation, Archer Midnight, Volocopter, Vertical Aerospace VX4, and the Terrafugia TF-X. Moreover, the literature serves as a feasibility study of the user requirements as well.

Another big player in the VTOL market which can't be overlooked is the helicopter market. Helicopters currently dominate the market for VTOLs with a market size of roughly 56.9 billion USD in 2022⁸. However, the CAGR is only 3.7% which is significantly lower compared to the eVTOL market, which has a CAGR of between 13%-27%. The VTOL market will also face more and more regulations related to sustainability as Europe gets closer to 2050, meaning there will be extra constraints that will make it difficult for VTOLs to prosper.

⁵Obtained by rounding 396 [km] up to 400 [km]

⁶Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.eurostar.com/us-en/about-eurostar/our-company>

⁷Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.nsinternational.com/france/thalys-to-paris>

⁸Accessed April 26th 2023, <https://www.globenewswire.com/en/news-release/2023/04/13/2645861/0/en/Helicopter-Market-to-Reach-USD-76-16-Billion-by-2030-Fortune-Business-Insights.html#:~:text=Pune%2C%20India%2C%20April%2013%2C,3.7%25%20during%20the%20forecast%20period.>

In Table 1.4, many different eVTOLs have been given with their specifications. These values can help determine the expected production costs, range, MTOW, and cruise speed from an eVTOL this size. Its main purpose is that it assesses competition.

Table 1.4: Similar Product Specifications

eVTOL	Cost (\$)	Type of eVTOL	Pax	Range (km)	MTOM (kg)	Cruise Speed (km/h)
Astro ⁹	-	Multirotor	2	32	360	70
VRCO ¹⁰	2,000,000	Tilt Rotor	2	120	450	338
Bartini ¹¹	-	Tilt Rotor	3	150	1,100	300
Joby ¹²	1,300,000 ¹³	Tilt Rotor	4	241	1815	322
XTI ¹⁴	-	Tilt Rotor	6	700	2404	555
Lilium ¹⁵	2,500,000	Tilt Duct	6	300	3,175	280
Archer ¹⁶	-	Lift + Cruise	4	160	3,175	241
Bell ¹⁷	-	Tilt Rotor	4	97	3,175	241
Alaka'i Skai (H ₂ -based) ¹⁸	-	Multi-rotor	4	640	454 (Payload)	185

Table 1.4 displays many eVTOLs, with their respective information. These give an order of magnitude for each specification that can be compared with Aetheria. For the Alaka'i Skai hydrogen-based eVTOL, no MTOW was found but instead, a maximum payload mass of 454 kg was found. The limited information found on costs is still quite important to be able to determine the price of Aetheria .

As for the segmentation of the eVTOL market displayed in Table 1.4, there are hundreds of designs available already, which can all be categorized into 4 different lift technology categories: multirotor, lift + cruise, tilt wing, and tilt duct (or tilt-rotor)¹⁹. Multirotors are drone-like designs with multiple rotors able to provide vertical lift and will remain in the same configuration for horizontal flight by pitching them forward. This is a rather simple design which is usually designed for shorter-range flight. Next, lift + cruise eVTOLs are fixed-wing designs that have designated propellers for vertical flight and usually a single propeller for horizontal flight. An advantage of this is the reduction of complexity for no additional rotating structural elements have to be implemented. Then, tilt-wing eVTOLs have wings capable of rotating in their entirety, which is beneficial for aerodynamics in vertical flight as the wing is in a low-drag configuration. Finally, tilt duct eVTOLs are similar to tilt wings except that the ducted fans or rotors have rotational freedom instead of the entire wing.

1.4.1. Costs

Regarding costs, another study showed that the cost of an eVTOL is expected to be approximately US\$1.2 million per four-seater eVTOL aircraft depending on an annual production of 100 units, close to US\$600,000 for an annual production of 500 units, and close to US\$200,000 for an annual production of 5,000 units [8].

A large difference between the team's eVTOL and existing ones is the usage of hydrogen. This affects the cost in a negative way as hydrogen requires more infrastructure to accommodate²⁰. Storing hydrogen in a liquid state would require smaller tanks, but more energy to cool, and vice versa for storing it in a compressed gaseous state. Therefore in the final cost estimation, a margin should be added for the usage of hydrogen.

There are three eVTOLs given in Table 1.4 with their costs, yet Lilium is the only one that is not a projection. Therefore using Lilium as a cost estimator for the team's eVTOL makes more sense. Lilium costs 2.5 million but can fit 6 passengers. This makes the Lilium slightly more expensive in terms of payload mass ability, as

⁹ Accessed April 28th 2023, <https://flyastro.com/features/>

¹⁰ Accessed April 28th 2023, <https://evtol.news/vrco-neocraft/>

¹¹ Accessed April 28th 2023, <https://evtol.news/bartini/>

¹² Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://evtol.news/joby-s4>

¹³ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://verticalmag.com/features/joby-aviation-evtol-spac-merger-reinvent-technology/>

¹⁴ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://evtol.news/xti-aircraft/>

¹⁵ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.lilium.com>

¹⁶ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.archer.com/midnight>

¹⁷ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://evtol.news/bell-nexus-4ex/>

¹⁸ Accessed April 26th 2023, <https://www.alakai.com/skai>

¹⁹ Accessed April 28th 2023, <https://www.einfochips.com/blog/evtol-aircraft-future-of-elevated-aerial-transportation/>

²⁰ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://simpleflying.com/electric-vs-hydrogen-winner/>

their fuselage needs to be bigger. Working with Lilium's cost and taking into account a lowering of the cost for a smaller fuselage while also increasing it due to the usage of hydrogen, the team's eVTOL has been given a budget of 3 million euros. This is including contingencies for production costs with the aim of lowering the cost to 2 million euros once economies of scale can be achieved. Now that production costs have been determined, the operational costs can be determined.

Table 1.5: Operational Costs of eVTOLs

	Lilium	Joby	Vertical Aerospace	Archer
Operational Cost [\$/passenger mile]	1.75	0.86	1.06	-
Price [\$/passenger mile]	2.25	3.0	-	3.30

Table 1.5 demonstrates the operational costs, and charged price²¹. These values have been roughly calculated by each producer at 25 flights a day, 100 km per flight, flying 10 hours a day, and filling 4.5 seats out of 6, excluding a pilot. These values are important to note as to stay competitive, these values must be considered. Joby Aerospace has even given the breakdown of their operational cost of 86 cents. They expect 22 cents for the pilot, 19 cents for maintenance, 11 cents for vertiport support/landing fees, 13 cents for the battery and charging, 9 cents for the aircraft insurance, and 12 cents for the sundries.

A few aspects to take into account when determining the operational costs of a hydrogen eVTOL relative to an electric one are:

1. Hydrogen costs more than electricity. However, hydrogen fuel cells have higher energy density than batteries²² so their overall weight might be lower.
2. Hydrogen fuel cells are more complex and delicate than batteries, meaning more maintenance can be required²³.
3. Hydrogen fueling infrastructure is not as widespread, so more infrastructure could be required²⁴.
4. Hydrogen refueling takes a shorter time than batteries, so less time needs to be spent at vertiports, thus reducing vertiport fees²⁵.

Using Lilium's operational cost of 1.75 dollars per passenger mile, and adding on a margin for hydrogen use, the operational cost for the team's eVTOL will be roughly 2.5 euros per passenger mile or 1.56 euros per passenger kilometer. Assuming a maximum of 1500 flights per year of maximum range with a full payload²⁶, this produces an operational cost of 3.744 million euros a year. The operational lifetime of a single unit is also an important parameter for designs. Lilium gives their jet a lifetime of 8 years²⁷, and Joby gives their jet a lifetime of 15 years²⁸. The user requirement for the team has already been given as 15 years, and considering the competition, it is enough to stay competitive in the market. Therefore, due to the production cost of 3 million euros, (at economies of scale) plus 3.744 million each year due to operational costs, the total cost of the eVTOL becomes 57 million euros.

1.4.2. Weight

When looking at the types of eVTOLs, the Lilium comes closest to meeting our user requirement in terms of sizing, because of the hydrogen tanks. This is important to keep in mind because there is quite a large range between the MTOWs listed in Table 1.4. Therefore for the weight estimation, Lilium will be used, but considering a weight reduction both for the number of passengers, but also since less/none of the electric batteries will be used²⁹. Using this, a preliminary weight estimation (MTOW) of 2400-2800kg has been used.

²¹ Accessed April 26th 2023, <https://www.futureflight.aero/news-article/2021-11-15/counting-cost-urban-air-mobility-flights>

²² Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.petro-online.com/news/measurement-and-testing/14/breaking-news/lithium-ion-batteries-vs-hydrogen-fuel-cells-which-is-better/58898>

²³ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.twi-global.com/technical-knowledge/faqs/what-are-the-pros-and-cons-of-hydrogen-fuel-cells>

²⁴ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://simpleflying.com/electric-vs-hydrogen-winner/>

²⁵ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=1bf1cbf0-ac2f-4b39-a3de-2df77a9a515e>

²⁶ Accessed May 4 2023, <https://aviationweek.com/business-aviation/opinion-there-will-be-blood-dissecting-evtol-business-models>

²⁷ Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://ir.lilium.com/static-files/e1912f16-b455-4929-a7df-f8b4dd5c2446>

²⁸ Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://www.sec.gov/Archives/edgar/data/1819848/000119312521053631/d135823dex992.htm>

²⁹ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.unicore.com/en/newsroom/fuel-cells-battery-difference/>

A range has been given because a specific value would be quite far off compared to the real MTOW that will be found.

1.4.3. Infrastructure

Looking beyond just the market analysis of the aircraft itself, feasibility considerations regarding the required infrastructure should also be taken into account. Companies such as Skyports, Ferrovial and Skyportz already have plans for building a vertiport network in Dubai³⁰, Florida³¹ and Australia³², respectively. Another example of a company pursuing a market share in vertiports is Bayard Vertiport Solutions, which uses its previously acquired knowledge of building helipads and heliports to now start building vertiports³³. On the other hand, Andrade et al. conducted a study in São Paulo proving the feasibility of using the existing heliport infrastructure for eVTOL use^[9]. Another advantage this study brought to light was the ability to alleviate traffic congestion in São Paulo. Although this case was specifically focused on São Paulo, it shows the potential of using the current heliport infrastructure to accommodate eVTOL traffic in combination with future vertiport networks. It should be noted that to be able to accommodate eVTOLs on any heliport, additional infrastructure must be built to allow for battery-swapping, fast-charging, or refueling the H₂ tanks, which will already be incorporated in any vertiport designs.

1.5. Market Share

The most relevant dates to look at, to assess market share, would be the end of the 2020s. This is when the eVTOL can be projected to start being operational. Many sources were found that gave information about the projected market share. These have been summarized in Table 1.6.

Market Share Projection Date	Market Share Projection Value (\$ B)
2027	20.72 ³⁴
2028	23.21 ³⁵
2028	24.1 ³⁶
2030	24.9 ³⁷
2030	30.8 ³⁸
2032	35.79 ³⁹

Table 1.6: Market Share Projections

Region	Region Market Size ⁴⁰	Obtainable Market Share of Aetheria
North America	55%	4%
Pacific Asia	9%	2%
Europe	27%	7%
Rest of World	9%	2%

Table 1.7: Market Shares per Region

Based on these studies, the team can project that the market volume of eVTOLs will reach 28 billion dollars by 2030. After examining numerous sources, the team believes that its eVTOL could obtain these market shares: Europe would be the dominant market in which the team establishes itself, due to the smaller market size. eVTOLs are not as popular relative to North America, meaning there is less competition but, of course, is more difficult to sell. Having increased the range to be more accommodating of intercity travel between large cities, the team feels confident in a rough 8% market share in Europe. The North American market is very promising, yet is difficult to succeed. The team believes that due to the long-range capabilities of the eVTOL, it has quite a good chance of establishing itself, especially on the East Coast where most cities are quite close together. The Pacific Asian market does not show promise in this context. Ehang is already present in this region, having had quite an impact, but their eVTOL has a range of 30 kilometers. This means that intracity travel could be dominated by them, but intercity travel could very much be in our hands. The rest of the

³⁰ Accessed April 26th 2023, <https://evtolinsights.com/2023/02/skyports-infrastructures-vertiport-design-for-dubai-approved-for-de>

³¹ Accessed April 26th 2023, <https://newsroom.ferrovial.com/en/news/ferrovial-aecom-agreement/>

³² Accessed April 26th 2023, <https://www.businessnewsaustralia.com/articles/skyportz-partners-with-perth-s-electro-aero-to-power-p.html>

³³ Accessed April 26th 2023, <https://www.bayardsvertiports.com>

³⁴ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/evtol-aircraft-global-market-report>

³⁵ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/evtol-aircraft-market-106298>

³⁶ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.imarcgroup.com/evtol-aircraft-market>

³⁷ Accessed May 1st 2023, https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/evtol-aircraft-market-size-trends-report-2023-2030-shraddha-desai/?trk=article-ssr-frontend-pulse_more-articles_related-content-card

³⁸ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/evtol-aircraft-market-28054110.html>

³⁹ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/evtol-aircraft-market>

⁴⁰ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/evtol-aircraft-market-28054110.html>

world has been given value as well as the Middle East is known for displaying interest in advanced aerospace technologies.

Assuming that the average eVTOL costs 3 million euros as was assumed for us initially, there would be 10,000 eVTOLs by 2030, giving an insight into how many units would need to be produced by this date.

1. Europe: $10,000 \cdot 0.27 \cdot 0.07 = 189$
2. North America: $10,000 \cdot 0.55 \cdot 0.04 = 220$
3. Pacific Asia: $10,000 \cdot 0.09 \cdot 0.02 = 18$
4. Rest of the World: $10,000 \cdot 0.09 \cdot 0.02 = 18$

From this calculation, 445 units would need to be produced. This is a feasible amount as the cost per unit will decrease as unit production increases. The team would begin focusing on the European market as stated before, then focus on North America, then the rest.

1.6. Proposed Business Case

To illustrate the use case of the Aetheria, the route from London to Paris will be analyzed and compared to the current best sustainable solution for intercity travel, high-speed rail. More specifically Deloitte and Morgan Stanley want to organize a real-life version in London of the "Winning in the Future of Health" online convention held in 2020⁴¹. In order to do so, employees from Deloitte have to arrange the logistics together with employees from Morgan Stanley in London, therefore they will have to travel the route Paris-London multiple times in the coming weeks. Finally, the route for both rail and Aetheria will be divided up in three phases: First Mile, In-Transit and Last Mile.

1.6.1. First Mile

An important factor in the first mile is the location of the vertiport. According to Kai et al., UAM networks are more efficient when using few centralized vertiports as opposed to many scattered ones [10]. It is then assumed that La Défense would be one of these hotspots, this can be justified by the fact that La Défense is Europe's largest purpose built business district⁴². Then a location, as well as the route from Deloitte was chosen using google Earth as shown in Figure 1.3. The location at the water was chosen for multiple reasons; the amount of people bothered by take-off and landings is minimized and the water offers energy absorption to a certain impact speed. The travel time and amount of interchanges for the first mile using Aetheria can be found in Table 1.8.

Figure 1.3: The route from Deloitte to the vertiport including an indication of where the vertiport would be situated. Where the "V" indicates the vertiport location.

Figure 1.4: The route required to travel from Deloitte to station Paris Nord where the Eurostar will leave from. Note figure is rotated by 90 degrees.

Figure 1.5: The In-Transit flight and route of the Aetheria and Eurostar, respectively

⁴¹ Accessed May 9th 2023, <https://www2.deloitte.com/cn/en/pages/life-sciences-and-healthcare/events/wuxi-healthcare-forum.html>

⁴² Accessed May 10th 2023, <https://www.ville-courbevoie.fr/1469/la-defense-le-1er-quartier-d-affaire-europeen.htm>

Regarding rail the first mile route can simply be taken from google maps, the amount of travel time and interchanges can be found in the summary Table 1.8.

1.6.2. In-Transit

The In-Transit phase for the Aetheria and Eurostar are both visualized in Figure 1.5, as can be seen the Aetheria holds a significant advantage due to the fact that it can fly the Euclidean distance instead of being fixed to existing rail infrastructure such as the Eurostar. This results in the fact that the journey for the Aetheria is twice as fast as compared to Eurostar. This is aided by the competitive cruise speed of 300 [km/h] of the Aetheria as described in Section 1.3. The exact travel times can be seen in Table 1.9 and Table 1.8.

1.6.3. Last Mile

Figure 1.6: The route from the vertiport in London to the office of Morgan Stanley including an indication of where the vertiport would be situated. Where the "V" indicates the vertiport location.

Figure 1.7: The route required to travel from King's Cross station to the office of Morgan Stanley using public transit.

Figure 1.8: Pascall+Watson's architects concept ideas of a floating vertiport in the Waterloo area in London⁴³

The last mile concerns the trip from the arrival station of the in-transit phase to Morgan Stanley's office. To fulfill this trip, a vertiport location must be decided upon for the Aetheria to land on. Similar reasoning as in Subsection 1.6.1 was utilized, and a location near Canary Wharf was chosen, as shown in Figure 1.6, indicated by the large V. Again, a location along the water was chosen. Concepts of this already exist, as seen in Figure 1.8. This concept was the result of a vertiport design competition by Pascall+Watson's architects. The vertiport allows for quick access to Canary Wharf compared to the last mile of the rail option, which requires two interchanges. The results of the last mile trip can be seen in Table 1.8 and Table 1.9.

1.6.4. Conclusion

The full journey has now been described for both the rail and Aetheria option. Aetheria is significantly faster due to the usage of the Euclidean distance but also the availability of landing at key hotspots comes to aid. This is because the Eurostar only arrives at the central station while the UAM is free in choosing its vertiport. So regardless of the location of interest, the Aetheria is statistically more likely to land closer to that location therefore decreasing the first and last mile travel time.

However, an important factor that has not been taken into account yet is the customs control for boarding the VTOL in Paris. Feldhoff estimated the processing times based on on the amount of check-in counters and the category of vehicle; Intracity, medium range or intercity. From the results the most conservative estimation was used such that a contingency is already applied.

⁴³ Accessed on 11th May 2023 <https://www.pascalls.co.uk/news/article/vertiport-design-competition/>

Table 1.8: Summary of the trip from La Défense to Canary Wharf London using the Aetheria

Phase	Duration	Interchanges
First Mile	11 min	2
Customs Penalty	30 min	0
In-Transit	1h 10 min	0
Last Mile	5 min	0
Total	1h 56 min	4

Table 1.9: Summary of the trip from La Défense to Canary Wharf London using Highspeed rail

Phase	Duration	Interchanges
First Mile	23 min	3
In-Transit	2h 20 min	0
Last Mile	32 min	2
Total	3h 15 min	7

Taking the expected cost per passenger mile stated in Section 1.4 for eVTOLs, the price for a one-way trip from London to Paris (343km⁴⁴) will range between €480 - €640 (calculated using Subsection 1.4.1) and will last approximately 1h to 1h15min. These prices do not really compete with the standard fares for the Eurostar, however, business seat tickets for the Eurostar trip cost €316,25 per trip. Although this is still cheaper than the eVTOL fare, one can now weigh the benefits of reduced travel time and exclusiveness against the slightly higher cost. Considering that the expected customers at first will most-likely be high-end businessmen looking for a swift commute, eVTOLs will probably be a highly appealing alternative travel option.

Thus finally, with Aetheria we tackle the market by addressing a majority of the largest barriers in public transit [7], which are the amount of interchanges, travel time and service frequency. Aetheria addresses the amount of interchanges by serving closer to your destination, travel time is reduced by a high cruise speed and a straight flight path and service frequency is addressed by offering on-demand service and a reasonable price range. Finally, Kai et al. concluded that UAM is most competitive on long-distance markets, therefore providing a more natural alternative to commuter rail and self-driving, further strengthening our market position.

1.7. SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis relates the internal strengths and weaknesses of the design concept and design team to the external opportunities and threats that exist in the VTOL, aerospace, and transportation market.

Figure 1.9: SWOT Diagram^{45 46} [12] [13]

⁴⁴Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://nl.distance.to/Londen/Parijs>

1.8. Preliminary Mission Profile

This section will give a brief overview of the mission profile that the eVTOL will perform. This section will elaborate on the different segments of the mission profile, together with their characteristics. A preliminary mission profile will furthermore give insight into relevant technical parameters, such as the energy required, range values, and cruise speeds. It has to be stated that this mission profile is preliminary as not all information to generate a complete one is obtained yet, but it can help as a guideline in the design concept generation. The mission profile is displayed below in Figure 1.10:

Figure 1.10: Mission profile consisting out of 9 segments

The mission profile can be divided into nine segments. First, the aircraft will taxi from the gate to the take-off pad. Following the taxiing, the aircraft will take off vertically and hover at around 15 meters above the ground. This value has been used by several relevant parties in the Urban Air Mobility sector (NASA [14] and Uber⁴⁷). After hovering, the aircraft will gain horizontal velocity and transition into horizontal flight configuration, after which it starts climbing towards cruise altitude. At this altitude, the aircraft will cruise at its cruise speed, for which the aircraft will be optimised. While approaching the destination, the aircraft will descend and decelerate. When the speed is sufficiently decreased, the aircraft transitions to vertical configuration and moves to 15 meter above the landing pad. The aircraft then vertically lands on the landing pad and taxis to the gate. In the case of an emergency or unavailability at the vertiport, the aircraft might have to diverge and loiter. If the aircraft is in the descend phase, it will climb to a new safe loiter cruise altitude and afterwards perform the same procedure as in nominal flight. If the aircraft is required to loiter while it is hovering, the aircraft first needs to transition to horizontal flight mode before it can climb to the new loiter cruise altitude. These loiter times have to be accounted for in determining the required energy stored onboard.

The segments of the preliminary mission profile can also be found in Table 1.10. This table furthermore shows an indication for the energy required during the mission, which will be of use in the concept generation and elimination. In order to estimate the energy required per segment, information about the segment power and time is necessary. The Lilium Jet is taken as a guideline, as it has the most technical data available and will be comparable in terms of payload and MTOW. This mission profile therefore represents an aircraft with the geometry and propulsion system of the Lilium jet, but with a hydrogen power system. The estimation for segments' power and time is explained below:

- **Ground Taxi:** The ground taxi segment is the least energy consuming segment. It is assumed that the power during taxi is 1 kW, which includes all the power that is used during taxiing. It is furthermore assumed that taxiing takes 30 seconds.
- **Hover Climb & Descend:** During hovering, the aircraft requires maximum power. The Lilium requires 2.2 MW during hovering with vectored thrust⁴⁸, which is more energy consuming compared to normal

⁴⁷ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://s3.amazonaws.com/uber-static/elevate/Summary+Mission+and+Requirements.pdf>

⁴⁸ Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://leehamnews.com/2022/07/29/bjorns-corner-sustainable-air-transport-part-30-lilium-jet-vtol/>

propellers. This assumption is therefore conservative. The hover time of 10 seconds is based on the mission profile from Lilium [15].

- **Horizontal Terminal Departure & Arrival:** This is the segment where the aircraft travels horizontally and transitions to horizontal flight configuration. A conservative assumption is therefore that the required power is again equal to the maximum power. The transition time of 20 seconds is again based on the mission profile from Lilium [15].
- **Cruise:** The cruise segment is the most energy demanding, as it takes the most time. According to Lilium [15], the cruise power is 10% of hovering power, so 220 kW. The segment time has been computed from the mission range (from Figure 1.2) and cruise speed (from ??) .
- **Climb to & descend from cruise:** The mission profile from Lilium [15] shows that the power usage during climbing is twice the cruise power and during descending half the cruise power. The segment time is calculated with the cruise altitude (3000 m) and the climbing speed, which is assumed to be 5 m/s. This is close to the value of 900 ft/min used by other eVTOLs [14].
- **Loiter operations:** During the descending phase the aircraft could have to loiter due to any emergency. The most limiting case would be having to diverge during hovering right before landing. The loiter cruise time has been set to 20 min, as this is the loiter time required for rotorcrafts in EASA NCC.OP.131(d)(3)(i) [16]. This loiter should be sufficient to reach another vertiport, as there will be multiple vertiports in one city. The loiter altitude has been set to 305 m, as this is the minimal required altitude from the project guide. The rest of the parameters are determined in the same way as nominal operations.

Table 1.10: Mission profile segments with energy breakdown

	Segment	Altitude [m]	Power [kW]	Time [s]	Energy [kWh]
A	Ground taxi	0	1	30	0.0
B	Hover Climb	0 to 15	2200	10	6.1
C	Horizontal Terminal Departure	15	2200	20	12.2
D	Climb to cruise	15 to 3000	440	600	73.3
E	Cruise	3000	220	5160	315.0
F	Descend from cruise	3000 to 15	110	600	18.3
G	Horizontal Terminal Arrival	15	2200	20	12.2
H	Hover Descend	15 to 0	2200	10	6.1
I	Ground Taxi	0	1	30	0.0
D'	Climb to loiter cruise		440	61	7.5
E'	Loiter cruise	305	220	1018	62.2
F'	Descend from loiter cruise	305 to 15	110	61	1.9
G'	Horizontal Terminal Arrival	15	2200	20	12.2
H'	Hover Descend	15 to 0	2200	10	6.1
I'	Ground Taxi	0	1	30	0
Total					534.0

The total energy required for a 400 km flight including loiter is therefore 534 kWh. This results in a specific consumption of 1334 Wh/km and passenger specific consumption of 333 Wh/passenger km. These values are still preliminary and are only useful to give an indication. The specific consumption values are comparable to eVTOLs such as Lilium Jet (256 Wh/pax km [17]), Airbus Vahana (380 Wh/pax km [17]), City Hawk Cora (315 Wh/pax km [18]), Archer Maker (389 Wh/pax km [19]) and Joby Aviation (198 Wh/pax km [19]).

To conclude, the required energy to fly a hydrogen eVTOL will probably be in the range of 270 - 800 kWh. This is calculated by taking a 50% gain and loss from the calculated value. This value is, among others, highly dependent on the aircraft mass, propulsion concept and aerodynamic geometry that still have to be determined. It furthermore does not include other parts of the power budget, such as air conditioning, avionics, lights and de-icing. These systems should be later be accounted for in the technical resource budgeting.

2

Requirements Analysis

Analysing requirements is crucial in order to categorise user requirements into killer, driver and key requirements to give a general overview of focus points during the design phase. Furthermore, these requirements are further analysed to derive system and mission requirements, which are significant for the creation of the design option tree.

2.1. User Requirements

As displayed in the *Project Plan*, the user requirements can be identified to be the following:

- **VTOL-USER-01:** The aircraft shall have a range of 300 km.
- **VTOL-USER-02:** The aircraft shall make use of hydrogen as a propulsion source.
- **VTOL-USER-03:** The aircraft shall be able to carry a payload of 475 kg (1 pilot + 4 passengers).
- **VTOL-USER-04:** The aircraft shall have a minimum operational life of 15 years.
- **VTOL-USER-05:** The aircraft shall have a cruise altitude above 305 meters.
- **VTOL-USER-06:** The aircraft shall have a flight duration of 1 to 3 hours.
- **VTOL-USER-07:** The aircraft shall be compliant with 'Emergency Landing' crashworthiness conditions specified in EASA MOC SC-VTOL.
- **VTOL-USER-08:** The aircraft shall be compliant with 'Survivable Emergency Landing' crashworthiness conditions specified in EASA MOC SC-VTOL.
- **VTOL-USER-09:** The aircraft shall have noise levels compliant with EASA regulations.
- **VTOL-USER-10:** The aircraft shall take-off vertically.
- **VTOL-USER-11:** The aircraft shall land vertically.
- **VTOL-USER-12:** The aircraft shall have a unit production cost lower than 3 million Euros.

As derived from the list of user requirements, the product that will be designed appears to be an airborne transportation system, as it is required to cruise 305 meters above ground. It shall have a mechanism to take off and land vertically, somewhat similar to how a helicopter would do it. The fact of using hydrogen as a propulsion source limits the propulsion units to hydrogen jets, hydrogen rocket engines or electric engines with hydrogen-sourced electricity. The minimum operational life will influence design decisions regarding redundancy and fatigue. The required payload capacity will directly influence overall sizing of the aircraft. The cruise altitude and flight duration affect aerodynamic decisions. The flight duration and range affect the required fuel on-board and feeding system. The 'Emergency Landing' and 'Survivable Emergency Landing' EASA regulations will affect the structural design of the fuselage, in order to accommodate for survivability measures. Lastly, the requirement on noise levels, as imposed by EASA will affect aerodynamic and propulsion decisions.

2.1.1. Key Requirements

Key requirements are the requirements which are of utmost importance to the customer. In this design, these key requirements are as following:

- **VTOL-USER-01:** The aircraft shall have a range of 300 km.
- **VTOL-USER-02:** The aircraft shall make use of hydrogen as a power source.
- **VTOL-USER-08:** The aircraft shall be compliant with 'Survivable Emergency Landing' crashworthiness conditions specified in EASA MOC SC-VTOL.

2.1.2. Driver Requirements

There does not seem to be any killer requirements in the user requirements. However driving requirements (requirements that will drive the design options more than average) can be identified from the user requirements list above:

- **VTOL-USER-01:** The aircraft shall have a range of 300 km.
- **VTOL-USER-02:** The aircraft shall make use of hydrogen as a propulsion source.
- **VTOL-USER-03:** The aircraft shall be able to carry a payload of 475 kg (1 pilot + 4 passengers).
- **VTOL-USER-08:** The aircraft shall be compliant with 'Survivable Emergency Landing' crashworthiness conditions specified in EASA MOC SC-VTOL.
- **VTOL-USER-10:** The aircraft shall take-off vertically.
- **VTOL-USER-11:** The aircraft shall land vertically.
- **VTOL-USER-12:** The aircraft shall have a unit production cost lower than **TBD** Euros.

2.1.3. Proposed Improvements on Driver Requirements

Some improvements and adjustments to the driver requirements can be made to improve the design beyond the customer's expectations. In this way, the market for the eVTOL can be expanded further. The adjustments made to the driver requirements are as follows:

- **VTOL-USER-01:** The aircraft shall have a range of 400 km
- **VTOL-USER-03:** The aircraft shall be able to carry a payload of 510 kg (1 pilot + 4 passengers)

As shown in Section 1.2, extending the range of the aircraft to 400 km has a large positive impact in the market reach of the final product and it is thus considered to be the target range. Additionally, it is found from FAA and EASA certification guidelines that the mass of a person used for certification purposes is considered to be 77 kg. Taking an industry standard luggage weight of 25 kg per person leads to a revisited payload mass of 510 kg.

2.2. Functional Flow Diagram

In order to get a good understanding of the functioning of the system, a functional flow diagram is very useful. The functional flow diagram is shown in Figure 2.1. The diagram analyses a nominal flight, thus excluding emergencies. Compared to a commercial airline, the functional flow diagram is quite similar. Differences arise in take-off to cruise and cruise to landing as then a transition phase is added. The diagram is elaborated on in the functional breakdown structure.

Figure 2.1: Functional flow diagram

2.3. Functional Breakdown Structure

In order to derive the functional requirements for the design, first, analysing what functions have to be performed by the product or its systems should be identified. An overview of different systems and the functions they have to execute can be summarised in a functional breakdown structure which is illustrated on the next page.

The functional breakdown structure (FBS) can be split into 4 main parts as level 1 category, namely the ground operations, flight performance, general design considerations, and disposal. These four level 1 categories further break down into smaller categories as level 2 which later break down into level 3, level 4 and level 5. The colour keys for levels 0 to 5 are orange, green, yellow, light orange, white, and gray respectively as can be seen in the legend. Ground operations refer to pre-take-off and post-landing functions performed on the ground as well as aircraft maintenance-related aspects. Flight performance relates to the functions of systems that help execute the flight itself. The general design considers the functions of the design itself which are based on the mission itself. Finally, aircraft disposal relates to functions post-aircraft operational life with a focus on respectability and sustainability.

Legend

- The Design - eVTOL
- Operations level
- Operations sub-level
- Requirements level
- Requirements sub-level
- Requirements sub-sub-level

2.4. EASA Requirements

In this section, a summary of the relevant EASA certification guidelines for the design of the product can be found.

2.4.1. Special Conditions for Small-category VTOL Aircraft

In July 2019, EASA issued a document specifically intended for small-category VTOL aircraft. This is due to the increasing appeal of aircraft in this category, that was previously not included in the EASA certification guidelines. This certification guideline is built upon the CS-27 "*Small Rotorcraft*" document [20]. This is because small VTOL aircraft share many characteristics with this type of aircraft. One of the commonalities is the maximum take off mass being limited to 3175 kg [1]. This value suits adequately the scope of this product, as the payload to be transported is only 475kg. Other aircraft of similar characteristics are found to be below this limit, and thus it can be assumed that the designed aircraft will be as well.

The *Special Conditions for small-category VTOL aircraft* document includes other aircraft-related guidelines, which are not present in the CS-27 certification guidelines.

2.4.2. Safety and Reliability Regulations

Emergency landing is a crucial case to consider with every flying vehicle since, unexpected scenarios leading to this specific case can happen at all times leading to dangerous outcomes. Therefore, aircraft should be compliant with regulations in order to provide as much damage control as possible in such cases. As a result, EASA, imposes a lot of regulations when it comes to certification of aircraft with regards to safety and reliability that the designer and manufacturer has to comply with. These regulations follow from the "Means of Compliance with the special condition VTOL MOC-2 SC-VTOL" [21].

The regulations are mainly split into 2 different categories of certification, namely, the "Basic" and "Enhanced" categories. The "Basic" category contains regulations that refer to the aircraft being capable of performing a controlled landing. Whereas, the "Enhanced" category is a build up of the "Basic" category with more imposed restrictions to guarantee a safe flight for emergencies, including landing. This category is imposed on aircraft that are designed to operate over populated areas or used for commercial passenger transport.

Furthermore, the VTOL is designed to operate over large ranges thus it will definitely operate over water environments. As a result, there are three airworthiness categories defined: limited over-water operations, emergency flotation and ditching [21]. For certification with ditching provisions, emergency flotation provisions or limited over water operations, the structural strength should meet the specified design criteria. For certification with emergency flotation or limited over water operations, the loading conditions apply to the buoyancy components provided to meet VTOL.2310 and VTOL.2270(c) respectively, and their attachments to the aircraft [21]. For certification with ditching provisions, the loading conditions apply to all parts of the aircraft. For certification for only limited over water operations, the aircraft should meet the design criteria defined for MOC VTOL.2310(b) Emergency Flotation [21].

2.4.3. Noise Regulations

EASA is in charge of certifying different aircraft in accordance to certain regulations. These include safety and reliability of the aircraft as well as noise, among others. In order to certify an aircraft, EASA's noise regulations verify accordance with ICAO Annex 16 Vol I [22]. Since the aircraft that is object of this design exercise may include design options that are unconventional for existing aircraft, EASA may enforce multiple regulations with regards to noise. The regulations that adhere the most to the possible design options of this exercise are listed below.

Chapter 10: Propeller-driven aeroplanes not exceeding 8618 kg

This chapter of the regulations indicates that, for a propeller-driven aircraft not exceeding 8618 kg as MTOM (Maximum Take Off Mass), the maximum allowed noise 2500m in front of the take-off roll is dependant on the mass as follows in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Maximum allowed noise as function of aircraft mass for propeller-driven aeroplane not exceeding 8618 kg

Mass (1000 kg)	Maximum allowed noise (dB)
M<0.6	76
0.6<M<1.4	83.23 + 32.67 log(M)
M>1.4	88

Table 2.2: Maximum allowed noise as function of aircraft mass for helicopter not exceeding 3175 kg

Mass (1000 kg)	Maximum allowed noise (dB)
M<1.417	82
M>1.417	80.49 + 9.97 log(M)

Chapter 11: Helicopters not exceeding 3175 kg

This chapter of the regulations applies to helicopters with a MTOM of maximum 3175 kg [1]. The noise at a point located 150 meters below a specified flight path shall be lower than the maximum values, as specified in Table 2.2

Chapter 13: Tilt-rotors

This chapter specifies the maximum allowed noise of a tilt-rotor aircraft. As opposed to the previously mentioned chapters, this one applies for more than one stage of flight. Additionally, the noise levels are measured in EPNdB, rather than dB. EPNdB is a measure of human annoyance to aircraft noise which has special spectral characteristics and persistence of sounds¹. For different flight stages and aircraft MTOM, the maximum noise levels apply as displayed in Table 2.3. These values correspond to measurements taken in VTOL configuration only.

Table 2.3: Maximum allowed noise as function of aircraft mass for tilt-rotor aircraft

Mass (1000 kg)	Maximum allowed noise (EPNdB)
<i>Take-off</i>	
M<0.788	89
0.788<M<80	90.03 + 9.97 log(M)
M>80	109
<i>Overflight</i>	
M<0.788	88
0.788<M<80	89.03 + 9.97 log(M)
M>80	108
<i>Approach</i>	
M<0.788	90
0.788<M<80	91.03 + 9.97 log(M)
M>80	110

2.5. Requirements Discovery Tree

In this section, the requirements discovery tree will be discussed and analysed, including the stakeholder requirements and the system requirements. The latter are further divided into functional requirements and mission requirements, depending on whether they are derived from system functions, or from the mission description.

2.5.1. Stakeholder Requirements

The main stakeholders involved in the design of this product are the customers, regulators, environment, passengers, pilot and investors. The requirements derived from all these stakeholders can be observed in the stakeholder requirements, within the requirements discovery tree. Each of the requirements has been attributed a unique identifier, such that they can be referenced at any stage of the design process.

In the stakeholder requirements one can observe that several parameters appear as **TBD**, meaning they are not yet determined. The list of these requirements are shown in the list below.

- **VTOL-STK-CUST-07:** The aircraft shall have a unit production cost lower than **TBD**

¹Accessed April 26th 2023, https://www.icao.int/Meetings/EnvironmentalWorkshops/Documents/Noise-Certification-Workshop-2006/Depitre_4.pdf

- **VTOL-STK-CUST-09:** The aircraft shall have a turnaround time of **TBD** or lower
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-01:** The seats shall have a minimum pitch of **TBD**
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-02:** The seats shall have a minimum width of **TBD**
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-04:** The cabin noise shall be lower than **TBD**
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-05:** The maximum body-vertical acceleration during nominal flight shall not be higher than **TBD**
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-06:** The maximum longitudinal acceleration during nominal flight shall not be higher than **TBD**
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-07:** The maximum lateral vibrations shall have an amplitude lower than **TBD**
- **VTOL-STK-VERT-01:** The aircraft shall cover a ground area of at most **TBD** x **TBD** m² at take-off.
- **VTOL-STK-INV-01:** The design shall produce a yearly revenue above **TBD**
- **VTOL-STK-INV-02:** The aircraft cost shall not exceed **TBD**

Some of these requirements can be estimated through the market analysis. From this follows that **VTOL-STK-CUST-07** translates to a maximum unit production cost of €3,000,000. Similarly, **VTOL-STK-CUST-09** translates to a turnaround time of 30 minutes or lower for nominal operations and 100% capacity refuel. **VTOL-STK-INV-01** and **VTOL-STK-INV-02** translate as well to a yearly revenue of €1,800,000 and a total aircraft cost of ownership of €56,000,000.

2.5.2. System Requirements

The system requirements are posed by two main groups, the mission requirements, which come from the mission description and characteristics, and the functional requirements, derived from the technical needs and functions of the system to perform as intended. In the mission requirements, one can find the main contributors to be budgeting, regulations, mass and sustainability. Each requirement is indexed with a unique identifier in this branch, of the form **VTOL-MIS-GROUP-(SUBGROUP)-NR**, in which *MIS* stands for mission requirements, *(SUB-)GROUP* is substituted by a (sub-)group identifier, and *NR* is substituted by the requirement number index.

The functional requirements are divided in flight performance requirements and ground operation requirements. The former are subdivided in structures, aerodynamics, propulsion, and power. Similarly to the mission requirements, each requirement is assigned a unique identifier of the form **VTOL-FUNC-GROUP-NR-(NR)**. In this identifier, *FUNC* stands for functional requirements, *GROUP* stands for the requirements group identifier, and *NR* stands for the requirement number index.

System requirements

Functional

Constraints/Mission requirements

Flight Performance

Ground operations

Budget

Regulations

Mass

Sustainability

Structures

Aerodynamics

Propulsion

Power

Crashworthiness

Flight Envelope

Structures

Economic

Environmental

Structural support

Vibrations

Lift

Drag

Stability

Controllability

Thrust

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-01: The aircraft shall store hydrogen in a tank that can withstand TBD loads.

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-02: The aircraft shall have a maximum fuel load of TBD kg of hydrogen

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-03: The aircraft shall convert hydrogen energy to electricity

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-04: The aircraft shall be able to store electricity

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-05: The aircraft shall provide sufficient power for climate control

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-06: The aircraft shall provide sufficient power the operating systems

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-04-01: The batteries shall be able to store TBD kWh in its end-of-life state

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-04-02: The battery temperature shall be kept in its operating window of TBD - TBD °C

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-05-01: The aircraft shall provide <TBD> W to the climate control system

VTOL-FUNC-PWR-06-01: The aircraft shall provide <TBD> W to the operating systems

VTOL-FUNC-GO-01: The aircraft shall have a means of ground movement

VTOL-FUNC-GO-02: The aircraft shall accommodate for inspection of critical components as specified in TBD to be performed in TBD

VTOL-FUNC-GO-03: The aircraft shall incorporate means to perform maintenance on all components that require maintenance

VTOL-FUNC-GO-04-01: The aircraft shall accommodate for hydrogen tank refuelling performed by one person within the specified turn-around time

VTOL-STK-CUST-07: The aircraft shall have a unit production cost lower than TBD

VTOL-MIS-BUD-01: The aircraft conceptual design shall be ready by June 27th 2023

VTOL-MIS-REG-CRSH-01: The aircraft crashworthiness aspects shall be compliant with "Emergency Landing" conditions specified in EASA MOC SC-VTOL

VTOL-STK-REG-04: The aircraft crashworthiness aspects shall be compliant with "Survivable Emergency Landing" conditions specified in EASA MOC SC-VTOL

VTOL-MIS-REG-CRSH-02: The aircraft shall have TBD emergency exits

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-06: Vibrations shall not cause structural damages when flying within the flight envelope

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-07: Performance data shall be developed for temperatures found in operating conditions (VTOL.2105)

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-08: The aircraft shall have a maximum operation speed of less or equal to 250 knots or 0.6 Mach

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-09: The aircraft must be able to withstand vertical gust loads of 9.1m/s (SC-VTOL.2200)

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-01: Performance metrics shall be measured in vertiport altitudes from sea level to TBD (certified take-off and landing altitude) (VTOL.2105)

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-02: The flight envelopes determination shall account for the most adverse conditions for each flight condition (VTOL.2110)

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-03: Within its flight envelopes, the aircraft shall show suitable stability and control feel, in all axes, with no divergent stability characteristic (SC-VTOL.2145)

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-04: If part of the lift is generated by a wing, the aircraft shall have controllable stall characteristics in straight flight, turning flight, and accelerated turning flight (SC-VTOL.2150)

VTOL-MIS-REG-ENV-05: The aircraft shall be controllable and manoeuvrable, without requiring exceptional piloting skills, alertness, or strength, within the operational flight envelope and must be controllable and manoeuvrable within the limit flight envelope (VTOL.2105)

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-01: The aircraft shall not be pressurised

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-02: Flight loads resulting from a likely failure of an aircraft system, component, or lift/thrust unit shall be determined (VTOL.2215)

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-03: The structure shall support limit loads without interfering with safe operation and deformation as well as ultimate loads (VTOL.2235)

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-04: The ultimate loads shall be the limit loads multiplied by a factor of 1.5 (VTOL.2230)

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-05: The aircraft shall be free from flutter, control reversal, and divergence (VTOL.2245)

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-06: Each part, article, and assembly shall be designed for the expected operating conditions of the aircraft (VTOL.2250)

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-07: The design shall allow maintenance of all components that require maintenance (VTOL.2255)

VTOL-MIS-REG-STR-08: The landing gear shall provide stable support and control during surface operations (VTOL.2305)

VTOL-STK-CUST-03: The aircraft shall have a minimum operational life of 15 years

VTOL-CON-SUS-01: The replacement of all critical components shall be every TBD years

VTOL-STK-CUST-09: The aircraft shall have a turnaround time of TBD or lower

VTOL-CON-MASS-01: The aircraft mass shall have a maximum take of mass of 3175 kg

VTOL-STK-CUST-02: The aircraft shall be able to carry a payload of 510 kg

VTOL-CON-MASS-02: The range of the centre of gravity shall not cause instability (VTOL.2100)

VTOL-CON-SUS-02: The aircraft shall use hydrogen as an energy source

VTOL-CON-SUS-03: The aircraft shall not emit greenhouse gasses other than water vapour

VTOL-STK-REG-05: The aircraft shall comply with ICAO Annex 16 Vol I noise regulations

3

Technical Risk Assessment and Management

In this chapter, technical risks associated with hydrogen eVTOLs are identified and analyzed. Risks are analyzed based on the likelihood and consequence of their occurrence. A strategy is made to manage critical risks and prevent their occurrence.

3.1. Risk Identification

In this section, various technical risks are identified and assessed. Technical risks can occur everywhere within the design and during eVTOL operations. Each risk is given a specific code which describes what kind of risk it is. STAB is a stability and control risk, STRUCT is a structures risk, PROP is a propulsion system risk, DEV is a developmental risk and OPER is an operational risk.

TR-STRUCT-1: Underestimating the operational empty weight (OEW)

The eVTOL market is still an emerging market and therefore limited data is available on existing eVTOLs. Furthermore, the implementation of hydrogen into aviation is also new. This introduces more uncertainty to the initial OEW estimation and hence it might be underestimated. Underestimating the OEW could have serious consequences as failing the VTOL requirements, decreased range, and increased loads on the airframe.

TR-PROP-1: Underestimating the energy required during transition phase

There is still a lot of uncertainty about the transition phase. The transition from vertical hover flight to horizontal fixed-wing flight is new to civil aviation. This could result in underestimating the time spent during the transition in total and hence underestimating the energy required.

TR-PROP-2: Propulsive failure

It is possible that for some reason the propulsion system fails during flight. This can happen during the hover phase, transition phase or during horizontal flight which each have their own risks associated with them. During VTOL operations, loss of propulsion means the aircraft loses the ability to fly as the fixed wings are not producing lift during hover and hence no upwards force is acting upon the aircraft.

TR-PROP-3: Hydrogen fuel storage safety

Hydrogen is a highly flammable gas that can cause explosions. Furthermore, hydrogen flames are nearly invisible and can therefore go undetected in the first instance¹. The fuel storage system could fail during crash landings, meaning that extra attention must be given to the crashworthiness of the fuel storage system. Lastly, the treatment of hydrogen fires and leaks also needs to be addressed by first responders as hydrogen-powered vehicles become more common.

TR-PROP-4: Loss of hover abilities during flight because of transition failure

Due to an event during the flight it might be possible that the aircraft is unable to transition from horizontal flight to hovering. This could occur due to the failure of the engine/wing tilting mechanism during flight. This would mean that the aircraft has to land as a normal fixed-wing aircraft which could be difficult if the destination is in an urban area.

TR-PROP-5: Overheating of the fuel cell

It is important that the fuel cell's temperature remains below the boiling point of water. If not, water vapour starts to form within the fuel cell stack which damages it. This makes cooling a crucial part of the hydrogen system. Also, the temperature difference used for cooling is lower compared to the traditional combustion engines where internal temperatures higher than 100 °C are quite common.

TR-PROP-6: Loss of Power

Losing power during operation could cause all electrical systems to fail during flight. This means that crucial

¹Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.osha.gov/green-jobs/hydrogen/fire-explosion>

subsystems such as the control unit are lost which can have large consequences. A possible reason for losing power could be the short-circuiting of the electric system.

TR-PROP-7: Not meeting hydrogen storage requirement

Hydrogen has a relatively small volumetric energy density and thus the fuel tanks will be relatively large. Furthermore, hydrogen will be stored at high pressure (gaseous) or at low temperatures (liquid) and can therefore not be stored in the wing box. This all implies that storing the hydrogen will be done in an unconventional way compared to kerosene-based aviation which increases uncertainty on the initial sizing.

TR-PROP-8 Running out of hydrogen and energy during flight

In the unlikely scenario that the aircraft runs out of hydrogen during flight, there will be no power available for the propulsion system.

TR-STAB-1: Center of gravity shift during flight

The center of gravity can shift during the flight due to unsecured items. The consequences of this are not trivial as multiple accidents occurred due to this phenomenon. The probability of this happening increase as more people unknowing of these dangers start using small aircraft.

TR-STAB-2 Aircraft too difficult to control

An unconventional shape might induce unexpected effects which will reduce the controllability of the aircraft. These consequences depend on the magnitude of the induced effects, so the aircraft might only be difficult to control which is not beneficial as some pilots might not want to fly it. But if the aircraft is totally uncontrollable no one will buy it and redesigning is needed.

TR-OPER-1: Damages during ground operations

The aircraft might be damaged during ground operations which results in repairs needed. However, it is very unlikely that structural parts of the aircraft get damaged as they are designed for higher load cases such as hover and transition.

TR-OPER-2: Failing to meet noise requirements

An important segment of the eVTOL market is the urban market and hence noise is an important factor to take into consideration. Especially as hover maneuvers are crucial to land and take off in dense urban environments. Therefore, failing noise requirements could result in exclusion from city centers and thus losing an important segment of the market. This risk will mainly come from the aerodynamic or propulsion side of the design.

TR-OPER-3: Bird strike

A bird strike is not a common occurrence for general aircraft, it could however have serious consequences as seen in the infamous US 1549 Hudson River landing in 2009. Bird strikes are most likely to happen during low-altitude operations such as hovering.

TR-OPER-4: Hard landing

Due to unexpected wind gusts it is possible that the aircraft has a harder-than-normal landing. It is expected that this will be quite a common occurrence as due to high-rise buildings the wind can become more gusty.

TR-OPER-5: Aircraft is too expensive

Buying an eVTOL can be quite expensive and maintaining one is also not cheap. Usually, this isn't a problem for most customers since it is quite a high-price aircraft. But keeping the costs to a minimum is still something to aim for since big projects such as the Concorde and the NASA space shuttles were all decommissioned due to high costs. This shows us that designing a very spectacular aircraft is not good enough if it is too expensive, since money still plays a big role in the aerospace industry.

TR-DEV-1 Numerical/model errors

During the design and sizing multiple models will be used. It is important that these models are applied correctly and coded without errors. If this does not happen then the final design solution might not actually satisfy the requirements as is thought.

TR-DEV-2: Assumption might turn out to be inaccurate

Multiple assumptions will be made during the design phase for unknown parameters that are needed. It is important to check at a later stage whether these assumptions were accurate.

TR-DEV-3: Underestimating power requirements during the transition phase

One of the difficulties when designing for the transition phase is predicting when flow attachment will occur. This is crucial as this is the moment when the wings start contributing to the lifting force. Therefore, there is some uncertainty with regard to how much force is required by the propulsive system.

All these risks have been assessed and ranked from 1 to 5 for the likelihood and consequence. The results can be seen in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2 and on the risk map in Figure 3.1.

Table 3.1: Scoring per risk before risk mitigation

Risk (TR)	Prop-1	Prop-2	Prop-3	Prop-4	Prop-5	Prop-6	Prop-7	Prop-8	Stab-1	Stab-2
Likelihood	2	2	1	2	3	1	2	1	3	3
Consequence	4	5	5	4	4	5	3	3	2	3

Table 3.2: Scoring per risk before risk mitigation

Risk (TR)	Str-1	Oper-1	Oper-2	Oper-3	Oper-4	Oper-5	Dev-1	Dev-2	Dev-3
Likelihood	2	4	3	2	5	2	4	4	2
Consequence	3	2	3	4	2	3	4	4	4

Figure 3.1: Technical risk matrix before risk mitigation

3.2. Risk prevention and Mitigation

With the risks having received their score, a risk mitigation strategy can be made. If something has a very high consequence but a very low probability, it isn't in very dire need of a solution and prevention plan. So the ones with a more dangerous score are taken more seriously. The prevention mitigation for the high-score risks is discussed below and is visualized in Table 3.3 and Figure 3.2.

TR-PROP-1: Underestimating the energy required during transition phase

Prevention measure: By performing adequate simulations and calculations, this problem should be easily prevented. This can also be done by using a safety margin to make sure there is sufficient energy. This risk can also be mitigated by determining the energy with worst-case scenarios in mind.

Contingency measure: In case this happens the range will have to be reduced as there simply is not sufficient energy to fly the desired range. Another measure would be to reduce the cruise speed, as this reduces energy consumption. However, It will increase the travel time.

TR-PROP-2: Propulsive failure

Prevention measure: To make sure the propulsion system will not fail, one can check or test the reliability of the engines. This can also be done by buying the engines from known and trusted manufacturers.

Contingency measure: To minimize the effect of an engine failure, one can simply increase the number of engines to make sure the system is redundant and will not catastrophically fail in case an engine malfunction.

TR-PROP-3: Hydrogen Fuel storage safety

Prevention measure: Designing for crashworthiness of the fuel system such that it will not cause a catastrophic explosion during a crash. Furthermore, the fuel system should be closely monitored so that parameters stay within their respective range.

Contingency measure: If the hydrogen fuel storage system catastrophically fails, the passengers and crew aboard most likely will not survive. Therefore, in this case, the team will make use of a controlled pressure release. This is to prevent an explosion.

TR-PROP-4: Loss of hover abilities during flight because of transition failure

Prevention measure: Making sure the system is as reliable as possible by performing checks and maybe even

making it redundant would prevent this as much as possible.

Contingency measure: If this happens, the aircraft should be able to perform an emergency landing while in horizontal flight mode. This should ensure the safety of the passengers.

TR-PROP-5: Overheating of the fuel cell

Prevention measure: Ensure sufficient cooling by applying a safety factor and designing while keeping the worst-case scenarios in mind. So, the fuel cell should be properly cooled, even in countries with high temperatures.

Contingency measure: If this happens, it is best to make sure the aircraft can still land without the power delivered by the fuel cell. In case batteries are present, one could try to use this to land vertically or try to land in the horizontal configuration.

TR-PROP-6: Loss of Power

Prevention measure: By monitoring the electrical power system and adding as much redundancy as possible this problem can be prevented.

Contingency measure: If this happens, the pilot will have to try and make an emergency landing. However, this is only possible if the control surfaces have some kind of power left or are mechanically connected because if they are fly-by-wire they cannot be controlled.

TR-STAB-2: Aircraft too difficult to control

Prevention measure: Use accurate simulations and approximations of the required control surfaces and perform adequate stability analyses to make sure the aircraft will behave as expected. Also, perform proper training programs for pilots to fly it so they are prepared in the best way possible. Also, do not opt for design options that induce very difficult effects which the pilot has to account for during flight.

Contingency measure: If the aircraft is too difficult to control, the problems will have to be identified and in case this is a technical problem (part of) the aircraft will have to be redesigned. If it is a training problem the training program will have to be updated to prepare pilots for the problem that was experienced.

TR-OPER-1: Damages during ground operations

Prevention measure: Make sure the personnel that works on the aircraft is properly trained, and make sure that refueling and unloading is not too difficult and will not cause big failures in case of a mistake.

Contingency measure: In case the aircraft is damaged during ground operations it will have to be repaired before flying again. The severity of the consequence does depend on what mistake is made. But for example, if the refueling went wrong it cannot fly since the fuel system is compromised. So, mistakes must be thoroughly checked to identify what the problem is. After this, a plan is set up as to how it is repaired and if it can fly before reparation.

TR-OPER-2: Failing to meet noise requirements

Prevention measure: By making use of certain types of airfoils for propellers the noise can be limited. It can also be prevented by doing proper simulations on vibrations to determine the amount of noise the aircraft will produce. Making use of special noise absorbing materials is also a way to make sure the aircraft complies with the noise requirements.

Contingency measure: If it is the case that the aircraft is too loud one can choose to redesign the parts which produce too much noise, this will almost certainly be the engines. Different engines might be used or more noise absorbing material can be added to the aircraft. So in short, the entire noise analysis will have to be redone to see what can be done to minimize the noise and still meet the requirements.

TR-OPER-3: Bird strike

Prevention measure: The main problem would be if a bird would fly into an engine and caused it to break. This can be prevented by not flying too fast, or changing the time at which you take-off to accommodate the birds.

Contingency measure: When this happens, an engine might be lost so it is shut down and the pilot must check if he can continue flying with an inoperative engine. If he can he will have to continue but be more careful, if he cannot continue or if there is no redundancy left the pilot must land as soon as possible.

TR-OPER-4: Hard landing

Prevention measure: Training the pilots by making them competent enough to land the aircraft properly. It can also be prevented by making the aircraft more stable in VTOL mode, so it still has good controllability even in bad weather conditions. The landing gears are strengthened to make sure these do not fail during hard landings and take up as much of the impact energy so the aircraft itself is not damaged.

Contingency measure: In case damage occurs to the landing gears or the aircraft, the damage is identified and an analysis is performed as to what caused it and if it was a human or functional error. The aircraft is checked to see whether it can still fly or needs heavy repairs.

TR-DEV-1: Numerical/model errors

Prevention measure: By using at least second-order accurate approximations, the numerical errors made during numerical approximations are minimized. Furthermore, it is important to keep track of the errors and make sure that critical values do not fall within the error margins. Finally, important code will be tested to reduce the chance of coding errors.

Contingency measure: Each model error will result in looking at the consequences of the error. Depending on its nature, multiple actions can be taken. Smaller errors could mean that the design will have a smaller means of compliance which can be excepted due to the limited time and scope of this project. Larger errors could warrant remaking models in order to produce correct results.

TR-DEV-2: Assumption might turn out to be inaccurate

Prevention measure: By using engineering judgment and prior knowledge, at least the order of magnitude should be estimated correctly. Furthermore, doing some initial research should help with reducing the number of incorrect assumptions.

Contingency measure: If an assumption is found to be inaccurate, all calculations based on this assumption should be revised. This means that a design loop will be followed and thus the final result will be more accurate. Reducing the consequences from failure to extra development time.

TR-DEV-3: Underestimating power requirements during the transition phase

Prevention measure: Perform proper calculations and simulations with safety factors. Also, keep in mind some worst-case scenarios such as engine failure during transition, bad weather, or overweight payload increases power needs. By keeping these scenarios in mind, the propulsion system will be designed to have enough power and ensure safety, reducing the risk.

Contingency measure: In case there is not enough power during the transition, the aircraft should be able to abort the transition and hover back to the take-off location and land again to abort the whole flight. Also, the situation will have to be analyzed as to why there was not enough power for the transition phase.

Table 3.3: Scoring per risk after risk mitigation

Risk (TR)	P-1	P-2	P-3	P-4	P-5	P-6	STA-2	O-1	O-2	O-3	O-4	D-1	D-2	D-3
Likelihood	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	1	1	4	2	3	1
Consequence	3	4	4	3	3	4	2	2	2	3	1	3	2	3

The risk map following the mitigations can be seen in Figure 3.2

Figure 3.2: Technical risk matrix after risk mitigation

4

Sustainability Analysis

The incorporation of sustainability is a crucial part in the acceptance of eVTOLs by the general public and should be taken into high regard. Sustainability holds three main pillars, each of which is to be critically analysed and discussed. These pillars contain the environmental, social and economical aspects, which are discussed in Sections 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 respectively.

4.1. Environmental Analysis

If a sustainable approach to powering the VTOL is desired, four options arise. These include i) Hydrogen combustion, ii) Hydrogen fuel cell, iii) Hybrid and, iv) Battery-electric. Burning Hydrogen still produces NOx which reduces air quality and attributes to global warming. When a fuel cell is used, NOx gases are not produced. An argument against using hydrogen fuel cells would have been that they require platinum, which is a rare earth metal. However, researchers at Imperial College have already developed a fuel cell that has substituted the platinum in the fuel cells with iron. Thereby reducing Fuel cell cost by 60% while making it future-proof and more sustainable, though there is still research ongoing to improve the durability and stability of this new iron-based catalyst ¹.

Both hydrogen combustion and FCEVs using hydrogen fuel cells lead to the production of water vapor. There is no consensus among scientists regarding the climate impact of water vapor production near the surface of the earth. Some argue that the increase in atmospheric water vapour can lead to changes in regional temperature and precipitation patterns. According to many others, unless the water is emitted in the stratosphere, the impact of water is negligible especially given that currently, the water vapor emitted from the combustion of fossil fuels is "10⁵ times smaller than the natural hydrological cycle" ².

The sustainability of an eVTOL can be analyzed by performing an LCA (Life Cycle Analysis). This analysis can be mainly divided into two parts. Firstly, the CTG (Cradle to Gate) analysis assesses the environmental impact of the production of the aircraft (except the batteries). This measures the environmental impact of turning ore material into an aircraft. The environmental impact is measured as Global Warming Potential (GWP). GWP is expressed in kilograms of equivalent CO₂ emissions per VTOL produced. Secondly, a WTS (Well-to-Shaft) analysis expresses the GWP in kgCO₂/kWh. WTS depends on carbon grid intensity, drive train losses, and the production of the battery [23].

4.1.1. Analysis of CTG and WTS

The WTS and CTG for different battery-electric VTOL configurations are shown in Figure 4.1. The cradle-to-gate analysis was conducted by simply taking the material emission index for different materials used to produce the aircraft (kg CO₂/kg) and multiplying it by the mass of these materials used to produce the VTOL. So the weight of the aircraft is inversely proportional to its sustainability in terms of production. It is important to note that the batteries used in the VTOL are included in the WTS analysis rather than CTG because, over the lifetime of a VTOL, the batteries are replaced multiple times [23]. It is also important to note that the relative importance of CTG with respect to WTS becomes negligible for VTOLs after 1000 hours of operation as seen in Figure 4.2. It is also important to note that despite the quadrotor being 1000kg lighter compared to the Life+Cruise configuration, it is less efficient in terms of WTS because more power is required in forward flight.

¹ Accessed April 28th 2023, <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2022/04/220425121110.htm#:~:text=Researchers%20have%20developed%20a%20hydrogen,greater%20use%20of%20the%20technology.&text=Imperial%20researchers%20have%20developed%20a,greater%20use%20of%20the%20technology>.

² Accessed April 28th 2023, <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.302.5649.1329b>

Figure 4.1: LCA for Battery Powered eVTOLs between 2200 to 4300kg [23]

Figure 4.2: Relative Importance of CTG with respect to WTS as a function of operating hours for eVTOLs [23]

WTS analysis shows that the GWP for eVTOL operation in Canada is half of the USA showing extreme dependency on the country's carbon grid intensity. The WTS GWP for VTOLs is given by [23]:

$$EI_{WTS} = EI_{grid} + \frac{EI_{grid}}{\eta_{system}} + \frac{EI_{battery-production}}{n_{cycles} \cdot DoD} \quad (4.1)$$

EI is the emission index in kg CO₂ equivalent per kWh. Each of the three terms can be evaluated separately for hydrogen and battery-electric VTOLs. The third term of the equation shows that the environmental impact of producing a battery is depreciated over the use cycles. The same applies to hydrogen fuel cells. In this category, the usage of hydrogen fuel cells is a winner over batteries because the fuel cell has a longer lifetime. Rather than evaluating this term in terms of GWP, it is more useful to evaluate it in terms of other types of environmental damage because the main effect of producing fuel cells and batteries is mining rare earth metals. Platinum used in fuel cells is obtained as a byproduct of mining copper and nickel automatically. Mining lithium required for batteries dries up the groundwater ruining the ecosystem in the surrounding area, again giving fuel cells the upper hand³. Next, the second term can be evaluated. Battery systems have an efficiency in the order 90% while fuel cells have efficiencies between 40-60% making electric batteries the winner in this category. Lastly, today, the most significant contributor to WTS GWP is the equivalent kg of CO₂ emitted to produce a kWh of hydrogen or electrical energy. Though this is the most important contributor today, it will tend to zero when the electricity and hydrogen production will become completely green. The green hydrogen production pathway is electrolysis. But electrolysis requires electricity as input, so producing hydrogen will never be as efficient as producing electricity, even in a zero emission future. Today, per kWh, producing, compressing and liquefying hydrogen may or may not be cleaner depending on the carbon grid intensity of the country⁴. From a GWP perspective, per kWh, there is no clear advantage of using fuel cells or batteries as

³Accessed April 29th 2023, <https://www2.deloitte.com/ch/en/pages/energy-and-resources/articles/hydrogen-vs-electric-cars-sustainability-lens.html>

⁴Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://hydrogen-electricity-production.blogspot.com/2023/05/is-hydrogen-or-electricity-production.html>

hydrogen and batteries yield very similar 'kg CO₂ eq/ kWh' values. However, this analysis is based on a 'per kWh' basis. This means that if using batteries or fuel cells can reduce 'Energy per person per kilometer', it will be more sustainable.

4.1.2. End of Life & Material Choice

Most aircraft are manufactured using composites and aluminium. The advantage to using CFRP is that weight reduction is obtained. For the Boeing 787, by using 50% by mass of CFRP on the fuselage, a 20% weight reduction was obtained [24], making CFRP more advantageous in the WTS phase of the life cycle. However, in the EOL, unlike aluminium which can mostly be recycled, CFRP is buried in landfills. The average cost of burying one tonne of waste to the environment in a landfill is \$9 [25]. In comparison, the cost to the environment of emitting one tonne of CO₂ equivalent of greenhouse gases (GHG) is \$185⁵. Thus, a preliminary calculation shows that using %50 by weight of CFRP to produce a 4000kg eVTOL to reduce the weight (hence power) requirements by 20%, the cost to the environment of operating the aircraft can be reduced by \$120,000 over a 15 year lifetime, operating 6 hours per day. 0.1 tonnes of CO₂ emissions is assumed per hour [23]. On the other hand, the 2 tonnes of waste buried in a landfill has an environmental cost of 2 · 9 = 18 dollars. This is a worst-case scenario assuming no CFRP is recycled. In reality, Airbus already aims to distribute 95% of its CFRP to the recycling industry by 2025 [26]. To conclude, the material should be chosen to minimize mission energy (hence weight), even if the material used does not yet have good end-of-life solutions from a sustainable perspective.

4.1.3. Environmental Sustainability in the Design Process

A lighter aircraft seemed to reduce the production costs to environment and better performance seemed to reduce operational environmental costs. Hence, designing a light well-performing aircraft makes the aircraft sustainable. During the design trade-off, increasing the relative weight of the criteria related to aircraft weight and performance will result in a sustainable aircraft.

4.2. Social Analysis

In order to be socially accepted and adapted, eVTOLs must comply with all different kinds of constraints. Among those constraints are constraints originating from regulations set by EASA on perceived noise at a specified distance from an aircraft. These regulations are stated in Subsection 2.4.3, where different types of aircraft are listed as eVTOLs have yet to acquire their own set of regulations. So, inspecting all requirements and estimating the most limiting noise constraint will provide requirements for the design options.

Next, the question arises of how much noise will be emitted by the design this project will opt for. Although the design configuration and propulsion system type is not yet definitively decided upon, a main differentiation can be made between electric and combustion engines. Little research has been done so far on noise emissions of electric propulsion systems. Hence, this type will be further investigated as it is also the most applicable to the design of this project. The difference in noise emissions for hydrogen-based fuel cells or battery-powered engines should be minimal as both provide electrical power and no combustion.

Berton et al. state that noise reductions of 8 dB are attainable for electric motors due to their ability to still perform well under low shaft speed settings in contrast to conventional reciprocating engines [27]. Moreover, the emitted noise of the propellers is highly dependent on the RPM, and not necessarily on the combustion of fuel. This means that in essence, there will not be much difference in using a conventional reciprocating propeller engine compared to an electric engine, except for the adjusted shaft speed settings Berton et al. described to attain a noise reduction for electric engines.

Taking a different viewpoint into consideration, social passenger acceptance should not be neglected when analyzing social sustainability. As the passengers are the intended users and customers of the designed eVTOL, the feedback and reviews they leave might be the difference between an eVTOL in great demand or the exact opposite. Consequently, one may wonder how passenger acceptance is best assured. Edwards and Price conducted a study on eVTOL passenger acceptance and came up with a set of flight condition criteria

⁵ Accessed May 1st 2023, <https://www.rff.org/news/press-releases/social-cost-of-carbon-more-than-triple-the-current-federal-estimate#:~:text=The%20study%2C%20published%20today%20in,estimate%20of%20%2451%20per%20ton.>

that are to be met to attain a 50% acceptable response rate from passengers for the flight [28]. The results are laid out in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Required design specifications to grant acceptable flight conditions [28]

Factor	Criterion for 50%-Acceptable Response
Cabin noise	< 80 dBA
Vibration	< .04g amplitude
Rate of change in pressure altitude	< 850 to 1,100 m/min
Pitch angle	< 10 deg.
Roll angle	< 30 deg.
Longitudinal acceleration	< 0.4 to 0.6g

From Table 4.1, some requirements can be redefined. In order to satisfy the 50% Acceptable Response, the cabin noise shall be lower than 80 dB and the longitudinal acceleration shall be lower than 0.6g. This affects the following requirements which are thus updated as presented. These new requirements shall also be taken into account for the trade-off of the design.

- **VTOL-STK-PAS-04:** The cabin noise shall be lower than 80 dB
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-06:** The maximum longitudinal acceleration during nominal flight shall not be higher than 0.6g
- **VTOL-STK-PAS-07:** The maximum lateral vibrations shall have an amplitude lower than 0.04g.

4.3. Economical Analysis

To get an accurate indication of the economic sustainability of the aircraft, numerous factors have to be taken into account such as the cost of production, transport, and storage. The aircraft refueling/recharging will be done at the vertiport, which will contain a refueling station. For the economic analysis, the assumption is made that both hydrogen and batteries are used as a propulsion source. As the fuel costs and other elements of economic sustainability are an important aspect in the trade-off for the design configurations, this findings of this section will be held in high regard when performing the trade-off.

4.3.1. Fuel Costs

In order to get an overview of where the consumer price comes from, and whether a decrease can be expected in the future, the costs of both the batteries and hydrogen should be looked into. The batteries use electricity to store power, which will need to be bought, making it important for economic sustainability analysis. The current electricity price is about 0.68\$/kWh for businesses in the Netherlands⁶ for grey electricity. The difference between grey energy and green energy is still negligible, as it differs per energy supplier. With an aircraft usage of around 500 kWh per mission, one mission would have an electricity cost of around \$340. Furthermore, the hydrogen market is just as important as the electricity market, as this energy source might also be used. The current production cost of hydrogen is 3.5\$ per kg. This is however grey hydrogen: Hydrogen produced from natural gas or methane without capturing the greenhouse gasses produced in the process⁷. The production costs of green hydrogen are currently slightly higher, at 3.7\$ per kg, but are expected to decrease to 1.5\$ per kg by 2030^{10 8}. This is the hydrogen intended for use in the design, thus whenever hydrogen is discussed in the upcoming sections, it will be assumed to be green hydrogen, given the relative importance of WTS with respect to CTG.

It is not sure how much the decrease in production costs will affect the consumer price of hydrogen. Since the consumer price is about 16\$ per kg⁹, much of the costs come from the storage and transport of hydrogen.

⁶Accessed May 2nd 2023, https://www.globalpetrolprices.com/Netherlands/electricity_prices/

⁷Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://www.nationalgrid.com/stories/energy-explained/hydrogen-colour-spectrum#:~:text=Grey%20hydrogen%20is%20from,of%20carbon%20capture%20and%20storage>

⁸Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-hydrogen-review-2021/executive-summary>

⁹Accessed May 2nd 2023, <https://h2fcp.org/content/cost-refill>

There is no clear estimate of the future consumer price, with sources giving optimistic estimations of 3\$/kg¹⁰, and more conservative with prices up to 7\$/kg¹⁰. The decline of the hydrogen price depends on a number of factors: the price of electricity which is expected to drop due to more renewable energy sources being used; improvements in the electrolysis efficiency and improvements in the storage and transport of hydrogen.

4.3.2. Availability

The availability of hydrogen is another important factor considering its economic sustainability. Grey/Blue hydrogen is currently mainly produced by natural gas reforming. This uses the methane found in natural gas which, under high temperatures, can be used to produce hydrogen and small amounts of carbon dioxide. Using CCS (carbon capture and storage) the carbon dioxide can be removed from the process. This is called blue hydrogen, but is however not renewable, since it uses fossil fuel. Using electrolysis, green hydrogen can be produced. This process consists of splitting water into hydrogen and oxygen. This can create clean and renewable hydrogen, which is preferable. This has a big availability, making it economically very sustainable. Furthermore, the learning curve of electrolysis is very high, and CAPEX costs are projected to decrease 50-80% by 2050¹¹.

4.3.3. Refuelling and Storage

Another important factor to include when investigating the economic sustainability of hydrogen and batteries is refueling/recharging and storage. A vehicle using hydrogen will need a place to refuel. At this location, a certain amount of hydrogen will also need to be stored. Hydrogen can be stored in three ways: It can either be stored under very low temperatures, very high pressure, or a combination of both. Currently, hydrogen gas stations (used for refueling cars) use a combination of cooling and high pressures. Since the hydrogen car market is expected to grow by 6000% by 2032¹², the storage possibilities can also be expected to grow, making this market innovative and sustainable.

¹⁰ Accessed May 2nd 2023, [https://sustainability.crugroup.com/article/energy-from-green-hydrogen-will-be-expensive-even-in-2050#:text=Taking%20these%20costs%20into%20account,\(real%202022\)%20in%202050.](https://sustainability.crugroup.com/article/energy-from-green-hydrogen-will-be-expensive-even-in-2050#:text=Taking%20these%20costs%20into%20account,(real%202022)%20in%202050.)

¹¹ Accessed May 3rd 2023, https://energy.nl/wp-content/uploads/tno-2022-p10111_detzweeda_projections-of-electrolyzer-investment-cost-reduction-through-learning-curve-analysis.pdf

¹² Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.globenewswire.com/en/news-release/2023/03/13/2625817/0/en/Global-Hydrogen-Fuel-Cell-Vehicles-HFCV-Market-Share-Envisaged-to-Reach-USD-62-88-Billion-by-2032-at-45-2-CAGR-Polaris.html#:~:text=%E2%80%9CAccording%20to%20the%20latest%20research,%25%20between%202023%20and%202032.%E2%80%9D>

5

Design Options & Elimination

In this chapter, the conceptual design is analysed and discovered. This is through a thought process involving a Design Option Tree, in which all possible aircraft options have been determined and explored, as found in Section 5.1. As derived from this, the feasible structural concepts are presented in Section 5.2 and the feasible power options are presented in Section 5.3. This will serve as a basis for the trade-off and preliminary concept in later design stages.

5.1. Design Option Tree

A design option tree is useful in order to explore different design options and configurations. The design option tree can be seen in Design Option Tree 1. As can be seen in the legend, the layers are separated by color. Furthermore, infeasible designs are marked with a red X. These designs are deemed impossible to use because they are either not developed yet, or are too crazy to be looked into. The unwanted designs are marked with a green X. These could be feasible but do not have the technology readiness level (TRL) yet to be used in the design, or are incompatible with the mission profile.

5.1.1. Structure

For the structural design part, the categories that have to be considered are the wing and engine positioning. The different positioning options for each category can be seen in Design Option Tree 1. The blended in fuselage engine positioning was discarded for unsuitability. There are three main types of materials that can be used in the structure of an aircraft: metal alloys, ceramics, and composites. A combination of materials is also possible. The use of ceramics was discarded as it is an unwanted design option since they are mainly used in high-temperature conditions which is not the case here, since metal alloys are sufficient to comply with the temperature of fuel cell options considered in the design option tree. Furthermore, ceramics are not used in the wings or the fuselage of the eVTOL since they are highly brittle.

Composite materials can be divided into two sub-levels, namely, the reinforcement (fibres) and the resin (matrix) used. The fibres of various lengths and the resin can be made out of thermoplastics or thermosets are shown. The choice of length of fibres and the type of resin will be further discussed in the trade-off section.

5.1.2. Aerodynamics

Wings may be used or a no wing configuration which includes helicopters and/or multicopters can be taken into account. It is not preferable to use more than two wings due to aerodynamic interference. A biplane, closed wing or tandem configuration are good options for a two wing layout. One or more tubular fuselages may be used and the fuselage-wing interaction may be a blended wing body configuration. It is preferable to use winglets because they improve aerodynamic efficiency. Furthermore, no tail, tail and/or canard configurations may be used.

5.1.3. Ground Operations

The ground operations play a vital role since the VTOL will not only have to land vertically but will also need to move around the vertiport. There are two main methods of ground movement: Self-movement and externally assisted movement. The self-movement is due to the plane having a power system that drives it around which can be done by using the aircraft's propulsion system, or by using batteries to power the ground movement. The ground surface movement can have multiple shapes as well. The most obvious option is using wheels, which can be retractable and non-retractable. Furthermore, the aircraft can be moved with the use of tracks instead of wheels, or the wheels can be placed on a rail. The aircraft can also be moved by an external force. This can be a transporter tractor, as used in commercial aviation or by humans since the aircraft has a MTOW of 2400-2800 kg which is not too heavy.

5.1.4. Crashworthiness & Emergency Safety

In terms of safety, two options arise. Either the whole VTOL can be protected or only the passengers. Since crashes may happen during landing close to the ground, the expulsion of hydrogen tanks, ejection seats, and parachutes are not viable options. It is also not very feasible to inject CO₂ into the cabin to prevent fire as it is dangerous to the passengers. Self-sealing fuel tanks also cannot be used due to the high pressure of the hydrogen tanks. To protect the whole VTOL, external airbags and collapsible landing gear may be used. If only the passengers are to be protected, a crash cage and internal airbags may be preferred.

5.1.5. Cabin Configuration

The cabin can be divided into two main configurations: One is where the passenger(s) is/are located on the same row as the pilot. This will give a number of configurations as shown in the Design Option Tree. Furthermore, when the pilot is the only one in the first row, the passengers can be placed into a number of different seating allocations. These all depend on the length and width of the fuselage. Finally, whether the cockpit is open or closed still has to be decided. This will be done using a trade-off.

5.1.6. Power/Energy

For energy production, multiple methods exist. Since, the mission concept is of a hydrogen-powered eVTOL aircraft, energy production methods are focused on this.

Mechanical, nuclear, solar or a hybrid combination that makes use of any of these methods is either unfeasible or unwanted and is thus discarded. The suitable energy production category is chemical, in which one can find combustion, fuel cells and batteries. Combustion of any propellant other than hydrogen is unsuitable for the mission, because of the user requirements. For the combustion of hydrogen, the explored options are hydrogen turbojet, hydrogen internal combustion engine and hydrogen-powered steam engine, all of these with an electric generator. Because it is an outdated technology, the steam engine option is discarded.

As sub-categories of chemical energy, we also find fuel cells and batteries. Because of the mission characteristics, and similarly to the combustion option, the only considered type is hydrogen fuel cells. Different options are explored regarding the type of fuel cell, the storage of hydrogen, and the refueling. Regarding batteries, only rechargeable batteries are explored. In this category, we find options such as super-capacitors, solid-state batteries, and lithium-ion batteries, with options for recharging such as on-ground recharging, battery swapping, or purely from onboard generators.

5.1.7. Propulsion

To achieve no emissions, the only viable options are battery-electric and hydrogen. Hydrogen may be combusted in a turbofan or be used in a fuel cell, to generate electricity. Electricity may be used to drive one or multiple tractor/pusher rotors that may be distributed along the aircraft. The propeller itself may be toroidal or conventional with or without pitch control. Lastly, the efficiency of the propellers may be improved using a swirl recovery vane or ducts. These rotors may or may not rotate with or independently from the wing and/or each other. If the rotor's axis is fixed, there may be separate vertical and lateral sets of rotors. The wing may fully, partially, or not at all rotate.

5.2. Structural Concepts

In this section, firstly, the desirable qualities common to all designs are explained. Based on these qualities, three designs are developed with competing objectives in line with existing successful concepts. Since power options are somewhat independent of the structural combinations, power options are not evaluated in this chapter. In addition, the location of hydrogen tanks (under wings or in cabin) is not discussed in the baseline report as an elaborate trade-off is necessary later in the design process.

The desirable qualities around which all designs are developed are listed:

- To ensure passenger comfort, all designs will keep passengers horizontal at all times, which means that the passenger cabin will stay parallel to the ground, within certain margins, at all times.
- All design concepts include rotors instead of gas turbines.
- All designs contain at least one main lifting surface and can become wing borne to reduce power demand during cruise which is important for a long range mission. In addition, all longer range eVTOLs

in the market have stationary wings.

- All designs feature straight wings due to straight wings being more aerodynamically efficient at incompressible speeds that eVTOLs are designed for and can help avoid unnecessary torques on the wing that would be introduced due to sweep.
- Since the wings will be straight, no blended wing body configurations are generated as sweep is required to ensure longitudinal stability.
- No designs feature a vertical tail as directional stability can be ensured with directional thrust. A vertical tail or V-tail can be added to all designs later in the design process if the propellers do not provide sufficient weather vane stability.
- All designs use all propellers for both the vertical mode and cruise because Lift+Cruise configurations such as EVE have lower range compared to non-Lift+Cruise configurations such as Joby and Lilium. By opting for a non-Lift+Cruise configuration, weight can be reduced as the number of rotors and motors can be reduced.

Based on the listed desirable qualities, three main design options are developed to be further evaluated in the midterm report. The first two designs resemble existing designs in the market that have longer ranges and follow two very different design philosophies. While one is heavily optimized to hover, the other is heavily optimized for cruise. The third design represents a compromise between the first two designs.

Figure 5.1: Design Concept 1

Figure 5.2: Design Concept 2

Figure 5.3: Design Concept 3

Design 1: Joby-Like: This design is a wing+aft horizontal stabilizer concept. The design comprises of 6 large tilt rotors. Initially, the use of 4 was considered but control would become nearly impossible under one engine failure condition so 6 was determined as a reasonable minimum. 4 of these rotors are placed on the main wing and the remaining 2 are placed on the horizontal stabilizer. A canard was not used due to ground clearance issues caused by having large rotors. The philosophy of this design is to have large rotor areas which reduces disk loading making the aircraft more efficient during hover. Lower rpms caused by having large rotors reduces noise frequency leading to lower annoyance. However, having 6 tilt rotors may increase complexity resulting in lower reliability.

Design 2: Lilium-Like: This design is nearly identical to the Lilium jet. However, the relative sizes of the tandem wings, number of fans and the size of each rotor is left as a design parameter. The advantage of having tandem wings is that both wings can create lift leading to a synergetic design. Rear wing is placed higher than the front wing to reduce wing interference. The pods of ducted fans that can be rotated prevent boundary layer separation and can reduce drag by increasing the boundary layer thickness. Ducted fans increase efficiency of the propellers and allow for noise amplitude reduction, though high rpms may still lead to high annoyance. Though the design may be inefficient during take-off due to higher disk loading, avoiding the large rotors used in the first design can provide better performance during cruise. In addition, the controllability of this design during landing and transition is the highest between all three designs as control can be performed by rotating the thruster pods and using differential thrust. Design 3 cannot actively tilt the wing to rotate the propellers to actively provide control due to high moment of inertia of wings. Even in the first design, actively rotating the axis of the large rotors to provide control during hover can be difficult due to gyroscopic effect. Having many small fans can make the aircraft more reliable in a one engine inoperative

condition and make it easier to certify.

Design 3: Wigeon-Like: This design is a tilt-wing design unlike the first two designs. To make a tilt-wing a beneficial option, the design features large enough propellers such placing the propellers in pods becomes unreasonable yet there are enough propellers to make rotating the whole wing more reliable compared to rotating each and every one of many rotors. Thus, this design features bigger rotors than Design 2 optimized for cruise and but larger number of rotors than Design 1 optimized for hover. This means that the third design provides a nice compromise between two designs that are optimized for the two different phases of the mission. In this design, the number of rotors and their area is an optimization parameter. In addition, the propellers can still be placed on the leading or the trailing edge of the wing. This design is a one wing + horizontal tail configuration. This choice was arbitrary. In a later design stage, if it is observed that tandem wings provide a distinct advantage while evaluating Design 2, a version of design 3 can be produced with tandem wings.

5.3. Power Options

Power is required to hover during take-off and landing, and to propel during cruise. The feasible options that were obtained in the Design Option Tree are discussed below. Two factors are important to consider for Power Options: energy density and power density. The energy density influences the possible range, while the power density is important to consider for the most power demanding phase, such as hovering.

5.3.1. Battery Only

Current eVTOL designs rely solely on the use of batteries in order to fly emission-free. These batteries used in eVTOLs have energy densities of around $300Wh/kg$ [29]. This is significantly low when a mission of high range is taken into account. In the preliminary mission profile (Section 1.8) it was obtained that the energy required for a 400 km flight is $534kWh$. This would, therefore, require a battery mass of $1780kg$, which is very heavy. In the future, battery energy density will substantially increase. CATL, the largest battery producer for electric vehicles with 37% market share ¹, has announced on 19 April 2023 that they will produce $500 Wh/kg$ batteries before 2024 ². With this energy density, the battery weight will be $1067kg$, a decrease of 40%.

On the other hand, using hydrogen as power requires much less hydrogen mass since hydrogen has a much higher energy density of $33.33kWh/kg$ ³. This results in a required mass of hydrogen of $16.0kg$. This difference in mass between batteries and hydrogen is a magnitude of 111. It has to be noted that a hydrogen power system consists of additional parts that add weight, such as piping, fuel cells, and air intakes. However, these components will not negate the advantage of hydrogen in terms of weight.

Conclusively, since batteries require a much larger mass compared to hydrogen, a much more efficient eVTOL can be designed by using hydrogen as a power source. Therefore, solely using batteries in this design will be disregarded and more focus will be given to hydrogen. However, it is also important that storing hydrogen will also result in large, voluminous structures which will be discussed further later on. In case a design with hydrogen can not be done, a more efficient iteration on battery-powered eVTOLs can be made, or a hybrid option in between.

5.3.2. Hydrogen Fuel Cells for cruise

This option relies on solely the usage of hydrogen fuel cells as a power source for the cruise (and climb/descend) phase, which is the most energy-demanding. Batteries will always be required for the following reasons:

- Energy is required for the start-up of the fuel cell. The fuel cell needs to be heated to its operating temperature before it can start producing electricity [30].
- The battery can power the onboard electronics and light when the fuel cell is starting up.
- Fuel cell throttle response is relatively slow and difficult to control [31]. For the pilot it is pleasant to have a swift throttle response, which batteries can provide. Furthermore, for active control with thrust

¹ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.pv-magazine.com/2023/04/21/catl-launches-500-wh-kg-condensed-matter-battery/>

² Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.catl.com/en/news/6015.html>

³ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.energy.gov/eere/fuelcells/hydrogen-storage>

vectoring and thrust differential, it is required that the electric motors can change their rotational speed in milliseconds. A fuel cell cannot always match the demand from the electric motors; a battery can provide the lack of electricity or store the excess of electricity.

- Hovering is extremely power-demanding. One would over-design the fuel cells if they were sized for hovering. The cruise power is an order smaller compared to the hovering power, so this task is better suited for batteries with a high power density. The hovering phase only represents a small part of the required energy, but it determines the maximum required power.

From the design option tree, it can be seen that there are four main types of hydrogen fuel cells that can be used, namely, the solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC), polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell (PEM), alkaline fuel cell (AFC) and phosphoric acid fuel cell (PAFC). All these types work on the basis of converting chemical energy to electrical energy.

The fuel cells in question all generate power along with water and heat, without producing any emissions making this power source fully sustainable. Thus, electricity generated from these fuel cells can be used to power an electric propulsor such as a rotor used to propel the eVTOL. The fuel cells mentioned approximately have similar efficiencies of around 60% but with varying power ranges that will be analysed further in the midterm report. Furthermore, in contrast to batteries, fuel cells have higher energy densities, lower weights, and faster refueling. However, using only fuel cells can result in a voluminous design, a constant supply of hydrogen, which is challenging to store, will be necessary in order to produce power. This has to be taken into account during trade-offs at later stages. Furthermore, fuel cells require to be heated in order to start functioning and generating power, thus heat must be supplied in advance to them. This can be done in the form of electricity with the use of batteries or external cables. Therefore, for a potential compromise between mass, volume, and start-up configurations, a hybrid option can also be a consideration.

5.3.3. Hybrid Hydrogen Electric

A hybrid electric eVTOL concept involves using both batteries and fuel cells as power supplies to negate the disadvantages of hydrogen such as low volumetric density. In contrast to the option above, batteries will now also be used for part of the cruise. The similarity lies in the fact that battery power is used for hovering and transition. At this point a comparison can be made between the different types of batteries to be used in a potential hybrid electric design, being: Lithium-ion, solid-state, and super-capacitor batteries.

One of the most important factors to consider when comparing different types of batteries is energy density. Lithium-ion batteries have higher energy density than both the other options, with solid-state batteries coming in second and super-capacitors having the lowest. However, solid-state batteries are developing at a very fast rate and have the potential to have an energy density of twice as lithium-ion batteries [32]. Although they have not been fully developed and mass production is expected to begin in 2025 [32]. On the contrary, when power density is considered, super-capacitors have a much higher power density compared to batteries since they can release energy much faster.

Safety is also a concern since in a hybrid electric option, hydrogen will be present on board. Thus having the safest battery option would be desired. Lithium-ion batteries contain flammable liquids, whereas, solid-state batteries don't contain any flammable items⁴, thus they are much less likely to cause a fire and result in an explosion due to interaction with hydrogen. Furthermore, capacitors are also relatively safe since no chemical reactions take place, however, they can cause problems if they are discharged too quickly.

In terms of cost, since the technology used in solid-state batteries is not yet fully developed and is still not widely adopted, mass production of solid-state batteries is low and thus their prices are relatively high. Therefore, lithium-ion batteries are cheaper since they are mass-produced and widely used. In addition, super-capacitors are also more expensive than lithium-ion batteries due to their longer lifespan, however, in terms of long-run considerations, capacitors can become more beneficial than batteries⁵.

To conclude, each battery type mentioned has strengths and weaknesses in different aspects. Lithium-ion batteries currently seem to have the best balance of all the aspects considered, however, the safety factor

⁴Accessed May 3rd 2023, https://www.etechnophiles.com/solid-state-vs-lithium-ion-batteries/?utm_content=cmp-true

⁵Accessed May 3rd 2023, https://poweruptips.com/lithium-battery-vs-supercapacitor/?utm_content=cmp-true

should be taken into account. On the other hand, super-capacitors and solid-state batteries have potential and offer promising solutions for future technologies and applications, which could be more applicable due to the eVTOL not being operational for a long time. A trade-off of what battery type to use in a potential hybrid electric design option will be discussed in the midterm report.

5.3.4. Hydrogen Turbofan

In a hydrogen turbofan engine, hydrogen is used as a fuel source where it is combusted, just like a regular kerosene-fueled engine, in order to produce power. This combustion of hydrogen does not emit carbon dioxide, which is a greenhouse gas, however, it does result in the production of nitrogen oxides which is an air pollutant. Therefore, the hydrogen turbofan is not a zero-emission design option, thus, it will not be considered further. Furthermore, using an electrical engine rather than turbofan has very distinct advantages. Firstly, electric motors cost less. Secondly, electric motors have fewer moving parts reducing wear and tear, making them easier to maintain, and more reliable. Thirdly, electrical motors are much quieter compared to turbofans making UAMs easy to operate in densely populated areas.

5.3.5. Hydrogen Storage Options

Hydrogen can either be stored in a compressed form or a liquid state. Compressed hydrogen is stored in a gaseous form in gas cylinders or tubes where gas is compressed by using high pressures (350-700 bars). On the other hand, liquid hydrogen is stored by cooling the hydrogen until it liquefies which happens at cryogenic temperatures (33 kelvin), and then storing it in an insulated tank. To compare how much hydrogen can be stored with each storage version, the amount of energy that can be stored in a $1m^3$ volume of each respective tank can be found. For liquid the mass of hydrogen in this tank is $70.85kg$ and for compressed (at 700 bar) $42.3kg$. As the gravimetric energy density is the same for both ($33.33kWh/kg^6$), the tank with liquid hydrogen can store 70% more energy than the compressed tank. So the volumetric energy density is 70% higher for liquid hydrogen as the gravimetric energy density is the same and the density is 70% higher.

This comparison indicates that the volumetric energy density is 70% higher for liquid hydrogen, so in the same amount of allocated tank volume for each type of hydrogen storage, 70% more mass (and thereby energy) of liquid hydrogen can be stored in comparison to compressed hydrogen. Thus, it looks like using liquid hydrogen would be preferable since more of it can be taken on board within some volume. However, it is also extremely important to look at the corresponding masses of the tanks for each type of hydrogen since weight is a very important consideration. For liquid hydrogen, cooling it down to cryogenic temperatures is challenging and would result in complicated and heavier equipment than compressed hydrogen. Furthermore, even though to take the same mass of hydrogen the liquid storage version would need smaller tanks, it would also need higher energy for cooling. The liquid hydrogen will also vaporise over time, requiring to vent the building pressure. This will decrease the usable energy. This weight and energy comparison will be done at later stages and used for the trade-off.

⁶Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.energy.gov/eere/fuelcells/hydrogen-storage>

Legend

- ✗ Infeasible
- ✕ Unwanted (low TRL, incompatible with mission profile)
- Top level
- Middle level
- Low level
- Sub level
- Sub sub level

6

Technical Budget

To efficiently use all the resources which are present during this project, it is essential to perform technical budgeting. During technical budgeting, all the major stakeholders, features, and specifications of the product are determined. These are then allocated a budget so the people working on the respective features know how much resources to spend on them. This increases the efficiency and reduces the amount of communication that is needed between the departments. For this budget, we will make use of the Technical Budget plan from Philips Engineering ¹.

6.1. Determine Subsystems and Parameters

The first step in technical budgeting is to determine the Critical to Quality parameters (CtQs). These are the most important technical features which define the functioning of the aircraft. These CtQs are then quantified and allocated to each subsystem. This way each subsystem team will know what their budget is for the CtQs. They are the mass, cost, thrust, power, and energy. The limit on these CtQs will greatly influence the design and functioning of all the subsystems.

The next step is to create a model of the product where all the relevant subsystems are described. The first subsystem is the Lift+Propulsion subsystem, we combined these as for eVTOL the Lift and Propulsion subsystems are often integrated into each other. This can for example be seen in eVTOLs such as the Lilium jet which uses vectorized thrust ². Another main subsystem is the power system. At this moment, it is not yet decided whether a hydrogen fuel cell, a battery, or a combination of both will be used. Since some eVTOLs use thrust differentiation between different propellers to provide stability, this eliminates the need for control surfaces. This would then cause the inclusion of the stability subsystem into the propulsion subsystem. However, since no choice has been made on this, it is still a separate subsystem. Other subsystems which influence the design are the structural subsystem, and the cabin as a subsystem. These subsystems are taken separately as the aircraft is designed with crashworthiness in mind. The cabin is thus seen as a separate subsystem since it houses the passengers and should be designed to ensure their safety.

6.2. Assigning the Budget

Determining the percentages is made more difficult due to the lack of existing budgets and literature on eVTOLs. There also are no guidelines and regulations on these topics so these percentages will mostly be determined using engineering judgment.

The structures subsystem will be the heaviest as it will comprise most of the weight to accommodate for enough strength. The power source will probably be batteries or cryogenic hydrogen and a fuel cell. The latter will require a cooling system as well which might be heavy. The control subsystem will probably not be heavy and might even be incorporated into the propulsion subsystem, then it takes no weight. The cabin will probably be quite heavy due to the crashworthiness, but as the size is not very large it gets a small percentage. The propulsion system is often not very heavy for propellers, but because wings are often big they will get a higher percentage.

The cost of the lift+propulsion system will probably be high if vectorized thrust is used. The power source gets also a big portion as the storage will probably make up most of it. The structures and cabin might be expensive as well, since it will likely be made of thermosets which are lighter but sometimes more expensive

¹ Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://www.engineeringsolutions.philips.com/looking-expertise/high-precision-engineering/technical-budgeting/>

² Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://evtol.news/lilium-gmbh-lilium-jet-7-seater>

depending on the desired shape³. The cost for the control subsystem also won't be very high but the structures subsystem follows the same explanation as the cabin department regarding material choice. The power source will have a high cost, as these new technologies for aerospace are still in development.

The thrust will easily be divided between the lift+propulsion subsystem and a small portion of that for control in case vectorized thrust will be used. The power will mainly be used by the propulsion system as well, the cabin will require a small amount for the passengers and the functioning of the cockpit for the pilot. The control surfaces will need some to retain controllability and stability while the power source might need some power for cooling. The drag is included since it will play a role in later stages. However, since there is no concept at this point a drag analysis can simply not be conducted.

Table 6.1: Technical resource budgeting for eVTOLs

Subsystem	Mass	Cost	Thrust	Power	Drag
Lift+Propulsion	20%	35%	90%	90%	TBD
Cabin	15%	10%	0%	2%	TBD
Control	5%	5%	10%	4%	TBD
Structures	35%	20%	0%	0%	TBD
Power-source	25%	30%	0%	4%	TBD
Requirement	3175 kg [1]	2M\$-3M\$	TBD	TBD	TBD

One should remember that at this moment in the design process, the team has not decided on a design yet. So these values are going to be changed a lot, the values in this table should in no way be seen as definitive criteria.

6.3. Resource Contingency Evolution

The preliminary margins are based on the current estimates from the engineers. For example, the mass has a hard limit of 3175kg set by EASA [1]. And since it is not expected to significantly decrease, a contingency of 50% was taken. The cost contingency was taken from Cost Contingency as the Standard Deviation of the Cost Estimate from Dr. Geoffrey Rothwell [33]. Final margins were taken from NASA guidelines on contingency management in aerospace systems⁴. And midterm margins were taken as an estimate between the two existing phases. Finally, the drag contingency is based on the Wigeon group [34], as our project is similar to theirs. These values might not be the most accurate but they give some first estimate on the contingency which will suffice at this stage.

Table 6.2: Contingency table

Design maturity	Mass	Cost	Thrust	Power	Drag
Preliminary	50%	60%	50%	60%	90%
Midterm	40%	50%	40%	45%	70%
Final	15%	20%	15%	20%	20%

³Accessed May 3rd 2023, <https://simpleflying.com/composite-vs-aluminium/>

⁴Accessed May 4th 2023, <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/6.2012-5273>

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